

D5.1 – Frameworks and Benchmarks	
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Abbreviations

Ab-D	Abiotic Resources Depletion	ME	Mineral Extraction
Acid	Acidification	MFCA	Material Flow Cost Accounting
Acid-A	Aquatic Acidification	MRS	Mineral Resource Scarcity
Acid-T	Terrestrial Acidification	N	Nitrogen
BBF	Bio-based Fertiliser	NRE	Non-renewable Energy
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand	OD	Ozone Layer Depletion Potential
Cons-E	Energy Consumption	OF-HH	Ozone Formation - Human Health
Eco	Ecotoxicity	OF-TE	Ozone Formation - Terrestrial Ecosystems
Eco-A	Aquatic Ecotoxicity	P	Phosphorus
Eco-F	Freshwater Ecotoxicity	PBCM	Process-based Cost Model
Eco-M	Marine Ecotoxicity	PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
Eco-T	Terrestrial Ecotoxicity	PM	Particulate Matter Formation
Emb-E	Embodied Energy	PO	Photochemical Oxidation
Eut	Eutrophication	QC	Quantity Center
Eut-A	Aquatic Eutrophication	RD	Resource Depletion
Eut-F	Freshwater Eutrophication	RE	Respiratory Effects
Eut-M	Marine Eutrophication	RI	Respiratory Inorganics
Eut-T	Terrestrial Eutrophication	RO	Respiratory Organics
FD	Fossil Depletion	S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
FFD	Fossil Fuel Depletion	Smog	Smog
Freshwater	Freshwater	SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
FRS	Fossil Resource Scarcity	TSP	Triple Superphosphate
GWP	Global Warming Potential	WC	Water Consumption
H&S	Health and Safety	WL	Waste Landfill
HT	Human Toxicity		
HT-c	Human Toxicity - Carcinogenics		
HT-nc	Human Toxicity- Non-carcinogens		
IAA	Indo-3-acetic Acid		
IR	Ionising Radiation		
K	Potassium		
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment		
LCC	Life Cycle Costing		
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory		
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment		
LO	Land Occupation		
MD	Metal Depletion		

Executive Summary

The present deliverable reports an overview of relevant frameworks and benchmarks that might support the development of bio-based fertilisers (BBFs) from biowastes within the scope of ReLEAF project. It aims to establish a basis for evaluating the sustainability and safety performance of BBFs throughout their production and use phases.

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to examine the potential human health and environmental impacts associated with the production and application of BBFs. This includes consideration of health and safety (H&S) risks, potential emissions, and main environmental hotspots. In parallel, a qualitative hazard assessment was carried out to identify the intrinsic hazards of substances to be used in the production of key ingredients in BBFs. This assessment supports the application of precautionary and Safe-by-Design principles early in the development process.

Furthermore, the present deliverable outlines a selection of relevant sustainability assessment frameworks, including environmental, social, and economic dimensions. These frameworks provide the conceptual basis and benchmarking criteria for assessing the overall sustainability of BBFs and their alignment with European regulatory and policy objectives, such as the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Farm to Fork Strategy.

In line with the European Commission's Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework (European Commission JRC, 2024) for chemicals and materials, in the present document are also described and explored the SSbD principles to be considered into the development of the ReLEAF's BBFs, promoting early consideration of safety, sustainability, and functionality throughout the innovation process.

Together, the insights provided in the present deliverable might be a reference for subsequent technical, safety, and environmental evaluations and may support the development of guidelines and decision-making processes throughout the ReLEAF project.

1. Introduction

Chemical fertilisers are widely used in European agriculture, but their uncontrolled application leads to significant challenges that may affect water and soil quality and human health. Additionally, the depletion of non-renewable fertiliser sources may also cause supply chain disruptions. Consequently, there is increasing interest in bio-based fertilisers (BBFs) as a more sustainable alternative. This shift towards BBFs is also driven by global efforts to convert biowastes (*e.g.*, agricultural and food waste, wastewater, and sewage sludge) into valuable nutrient sources. This approach supports the circular economy strategy proposed by the European Commission in 2014 (Kurniawati et al., 2023).

The ReLEAF Project (Leitat, 2025) is a European Union's CBE JU Innovation Action, which seeks to develop and demonstrate the environmental and agronomic performance of innovative BBFs produced using waste streams such as sewage sludge, fish processing wastewater and sludge, mixed food waste, and agri-food residues.

To ensure the safety and sustainability of intermediary products to be used in (a) the BBFs formulations and (b) Final BBFs (products), the WP5 – *Environmental, economic and social sustainability assessment* – aims, in the first stage, to provide insights to optimise BBF production according to environmental aspects in an early stage of the development. Then, this WP will assess the techno-economic, environmental and social impacts of the different BBFs developed. With this sustainability assessment, it will be possible to elaborate an integrated life cycle inventory associated with the production and use of BBFs and identify potential hotspots. Finally, the results of this WP will feed WP6, namely T6.12 – *Development of recommendations to advance the SSbD*.

Specifically, Task 5.1 - *Analytical framework and benchmarks for optimisation* - aims to identify potential sources of health and environmental impacts associated with the development of new BBFs at the very early stage of the development. In this context, it is essential to assess the potential human health risks associated with the production and use of BBFs, particularly those arising from occupational exposure, consumer contact, and broader public health implications, given the presence of biological, chemical, and particulate contaminants throughout their lifecycle.

To meet the goals of this task and support ReLEAF partners in their decision-making process, this deliverable has three main aims:

- Highlight the main environmental concerns associated with BBF production and use, as well as their functionality, scope of application, and benchmark based on a literature review.
- Perform a qualitative assessment of the safety of chemicals and materials used during BBFs' formulation, providing guidance for a successful safety and sustainable assessment outcome.
- Describe the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Cost (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA) frameworks, which will be performed along the project in subsequent tasks.

In this context, this deliverable is structured as follows. Section 2 briefly presents the methodologies carried out during the literature review, the data-gathering process, and qualitative safety assessment. Section 3 depicts the main findings from these studies, and the sustainability frameworks are outlined in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 highlights the key conclusions and suggestions for future work.

2. Methodology

This section describes the methodologies used for the literature review, preliminary data gathering, and qualitative safety assessment. The different phases of the methodology implemented to carry out the present work are illustrated in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1 - Methodology diagram implemented in the present study.

2.1. Literature review

A literature review was performed to give partners feedback about the potential environmental impacts of BBFs and occupational health and safety (H&S) issues associated with the production of ingredients that are relevant to produce ReLEAF's BBFs.

Considering the **environmental implications of BBFs**, a literature review was carried out (Figure 2.2) to understand the main benefits and drawbacks of producing and using them. To map the advantages and issues associated with BBFs, a preliminary search was performed in July 2024 and updated in September 2024 using Scopus search engine. A final update in the keywords string was conducted in February 2025 based on the experts' knowledge. In the end, a sample of 343 articles was achieved. Additionally, the string of words presented in Figure 2.2 with the keywords (i) "wastes" and (ii) "by-

products" was also evaluated during the literature review process. However, the sample was quite large, consisting of 19 000 articles, as it included all studies related to the environmental assessment of different wastes and by-products. Thus, to narrow the scope of the literature review, it was decided to exclude these two keywords.

After choosing the sample of analysis, the articles were filtered according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria presented in Table 2.1, using Rayyan web platform (Rayyan, 2022). From the papers included after filtering, 22 articles could not be retrieved or were in a foreign language. Afterwards, the included papers (189) were labelled regarding the type of paper, assessments performed by the authors, raw materials considered, boundaries, functional units and, when possible, benchmark used for the comparison analysis with BBFs.

Table 2.1 - Inclusion and exclusion criteria considered in the literature review - Environmental Analysis.

Inclusion	Exclusion
Papers that evaluate BBFs production, directly or indirectly.	Review papers (analysed separately).
	Research papers that are not performing sustainability studies (e.g., environmental assessment).
	Conference books of proceedings.

Figure 2.2 - Methodology used for the literature review performed.

Moreover, the articles were divided according to the role which BBFs take within the sustainability assessments analysed, *i.e.*, BBFs as co-/by-product, BBFs as consumable, BBFs as main product. Finally, the most relevant papers were analysed to extract the desired information. The main results of the literature review will be detailed in Section 3.

2.2. Preliminary Data Gathering

Simultaneously with the literature review process, a preliminary questionnaire was developed (Figure 2.3). Moreover, a preliminary flowchart (Figure 2.4) of the production processes carried out within

the ReLEAF project was requested. The goal of this preliminary data gathering is to serve as a basis for (1) the qualitative safety assessment, and (2) the development of further tasks such as T5.2 (*Techno-economic assessment*), T5.3 (*Environmental life cycle assessment of production*), T5.4 (*Social life-cycle assessment*), T5.5 (*Comparative environmental life cycle assessment of product use*), and T6.2 (*Development of recommendations to advance the SSbD framework*). Through this process, initial information was collected concerning the production processes across the supply chains of BBFs. It is important to note that, as the ReLEAF project is currently in its first year, many of the production processes and materials have yet to be fully defined and are still under development towards their final configurations. Given the significant level of uncertainty at this stage, relevant literature was consulted to support the information-gathering process.

This questionnaire was prepared by ISQ under the scope of HORIZON JU-CBE-2021 ReLeaf project for the activities related with WPS

ReLEAF Questionnaire on Health, Safety and Environmental aspects Confidential information - ISQ

This questionnaire is presented to the partners the ReLeaf project involved in the production, processing, handling or use of BBFs. The main objective of this questionnaire is to gather sufficient information for a preliminary assessment materials and processes, to identify potential concerns to the human H&S, emission sources and exposure scenarios. Moreover, this action is also part of a first step.

The overall set of information to be collected covers different aspects, as listed below:

- Production process;
- Raw materials which are used as input for the process (leaf), and the main intermediate and final products (chemicals/materials used as inputs in the production process, the main intermediate products (chemicals/materials) and final products (resulting from processing));
- Materials quality control, maintenance and cleaning procedures linked to the technology and development of ReLeaf;
- Waste generated by the process (waste management and re-use or recycling procedures);
- Other HSE aspects.

Note: If you are involved in more than one stage of the BBFs production process or if you contribute to the production of different ingredients within the same stage, fill in a new "HSE Asses." sheet for each one.

Although it is preferable to provide the most detailed information possible for each question, for the cases that no answer can be provided, please fill with "Not applicable" n.a., "Unavailable" u.a., "Not observed" n.o. or "To be defined" tbd.

We kindly request, when possible, to provide as images from the relevant facilities sites, materials, products and protective measures.

Additionally, please be aware that answering this questionnaire may take some time, and for that, we would like to acknowledge the commitment of all partners in this task, since the ISQ study is fully dependent on the information provided. Conducting the assessment as accurate as possible, will not only benefit those directly involved ReLeaf project, but also the general community as ReLeaf will be able to offer to the market solutions with safety and sustainability considerations, from the conception phases till the final solution.

In case of any questions related with this questionnaire or task 5.1, please feel free to contact us: [Carla Martins - efmarlins@logat.com](mailto:Carla.Martins-efmarlins@logat.com) and [A. Rita Aberto - ansores@logat.com](mailto:A.Rita.Aberto-ansores@logat.com).

If you produce more than one ingredient to be included in BBFs formulation, please fill in a new ball

RELEAF HSE (INFORMATION GATHERING)								
STAGE OF THE BBF: PRODUCTION PROCESS BY WHICH THE COMPANY IS INVOLVED <i>(Processing of leaves, juice and pulp, Biopolymer extraction and production, or other ingredients, Formulation and production of controlled-release BBFs, other)</i>								
If you indicated "other", please indicate which one:								
PARTNER NAME								
BBF PRODUCT <i>(Please indicate the name of the BBF product to which your company/ partner is contributing)</i>								
PROCESS FLOWCHART <i>(Layout, pictures or videos of the facility)</i>								
OPERATIONAL CONDITIONS								
STEPS OF THE PROCESS AND OTHER RELATED ACTIVITIES <i>(According with the process description made above)</i> <i>Please include also the steps/activities after the product is obtained, e.g. cleaning, quality control - technical support, packaging equipment</i>	NAME	VARIABLES						
	1	Description Task Duration Frequency N° workers Average duration of workers intervention Other						
	2	Description Task Duration Frequency N° workers Average duration of workers intervention Other						
	3	Description Task Duration Frequency N° workers Average duration of workers intervention Other						
	4	Description Task Duration Frequency N° workers						
	NAME, CAS NUMBER or EINECS NUMBER	STEP OF THE PROCESS IN WHICH IT IS INVOLVED <i>(in which it is added, produced...)</i>	CONCENTRATION	QUANTITY USED	DOES THE STAFF/WORKER CONTACT THE CHEMICAL/PRODUCT/MATERIAL? (YES/NO) <i>HOW/UNDER WHAT CIRCUMSTANCES?</i>	OTHER RELEVANT CHARACTERISTICS	SDS (YES/NO)	
	CHEMICALS/ MATERIALS <i>(fill all substances, including those required as inputs, intermediate and final products)</i> <i>Include additional rows if needed.</i> <i>Please provide the MSDS (in English)</i>							
	NAME	FUNCTION <i>(brief description)</i>	INDICATE THE STEP OF THE PROCESS IN WHICH IT IS INVOLVED	EC CONFORMITY DECLARATION (YES/NO)	DOES IT REQUIRE INTERACTION WITH THE WORKER? IF SO, EXPLAIN HOW THIS INTERACTION IS?	DOES THE OPERATION OF THE EQUIPMENT / MACHINE CAUSE AN INCREASE IN TEMPERATURE, PRESSURE, ETC.? IDENTIFY	PRESSURE EQUIPMENT? PLEASE INDICATE ANOTHER CHARACTERISTIC THAT YOU CONSIDER RELEVANT TO THE H&S OF WORKERS.	
	EQUIPMENT <i>(fill all equipment, including those required during regular operations and those identified/ proposed for the ReLeaf project)</i> <i>Include additional rows if needed)</i>							
	NAME	ORIGIN OF WASTE / STEP OF THE PROCESS?	QUANTITY	CONCENTRATION/COMPOSITION	DESTINATION <i>(Recycling/Recovery/Disposal)</i>	WASTE MANAGEMENT MEASURES <i>(Briefly describe how waste is managed at your facility, and if a company is contracted to treat the waste, how it is managed at the facility until it is collected)</i>	Comments	
	WASTE							

Figure 2.3 - Preliminary questionnaire template shared with ReLEAF partners.

Figure 2.4 - Preliminary flowchart template shared with ReLEAF partners.

After receiving the completed questionnaires, which included the preliminary flowcharts and other relevant information, several bilateral meetings were held, and emails were exchanged to clarify any doubts. These questionnaires and flowcharts will be further studied within the scope of different tasks within the WP5 and WP6, and a more detailed production process of each intermediary product and BBF will be included in future deliverables, such as D5.3 - *Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of BBFs production*.

2.3. Qualitative hazard assessment

Chemicals are essential to modern life, playing a critical role across various sectors and enabling technological innovation. However, some substances possess hazardous properties that can adversely affect human health and the environment. In this context, and in line with the European Commission's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, which advocates for the development and use of safer and more sustainable chemicals, the early identification of intrinsic hazards is fundamental. Hazard identification, as promoted under European regulatory frameworks such as the REACH Regulation (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals), is a key component in characterising chemical risks. This process supports the implementation of appropriate risk management measures across the entire life cycle of a substance.

2.3.1. Principles of Safe and Sustainable by Design

Since the ReLEAF project aims to produce ingredients and formulate BBFs through the optimisation of new technologies to efficiently recover valuable nutrients, biostimulants, and other products from bio-waste, it is important to align with the European Commission's safe and sustainable by design framework.

The **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)** framework, developed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC), provides a structured methodology to design chemicals and materials that are inherently safe and sustainable throughout their life cycle (European Commission JRC, 2023). The framework supports the European Green Deal goals by promoting innovations that reduce risks to human health and the environment while enhancing resource efficiency and circularity.

The Recommendation (EU) 2022/2510 (European Commission, 2022) highlights several key design principles:

1. Material Efficiency
 - **Definition:** This principle focuses on incorporating all chemicals or materials used in a process into the final product or fully recovering them within the process. This approach reduces raw material usage and waste generation.
 - **Examples of Actions:** Maximise yield during reactions, recover unreacted chemicals, select materials and processes that minimise waste, and identify and minimise the use of critical raw materials.
 2. Minimise the Use of Hazardous Chemicals or Materials
 - **Definition:** The goal is to maintain product functionality while reducing or completely avoiding hazardous chemicals or materials.
 - **Examples of Actions:** Use technology to avoid exposure, reduce or eliminate hazardous chemicals in production processes, and eliminate hazardous chemicals in final products.
 3. Design for Energy Efficiency
 - **Definition:** This principle aims to minimise the energy required to produce and use chemicals or materials throughout the production process and supply chain.
 - **Examples of Actions:** Develop less energy-intensive processes, maximise energy reuse, reduce production steps, use catalysts, and select lower temperature reaction pathways.
 4. Use Renewable Sources
 - **Definition:** Emphasises conserving resources by using renewable materials and energy sources.
 - **Examples of Actions:** Promote renewable feedstocks, use circular processes, avoid land competition, and utilise renewable energy resources with low carbon emissions.
 5. Prevent and Avoid Hazardous Emissions
 - **Definition:** Focuses on applying technologies to minimise or avoid hazardous emissions or the release of pollutants into the environment.
 - **Examples of Actions:** Select materials or processes that minimise hazardous waste, emissions, and by-products.
 6. Design for End of Life
 - **Definition:** This principle involves designing chemicals and materials to break down into non-hazardous substances after their useful life.
-

- **Examples of Actions:** Design for re-use, waste collection, sorting, recycling/upcycling, and select materials that are durable, easy to separate, valuable after use, and fully biodegradable.

7. Consider the Whole Life Cycle

- **Definition:** Applying design principles throughout the entire life cycle, from raw material supply to the final product's end of life.
- **Examples of Actions:** Use reusable packaging, implement energy-efficient logistics, and reduce transport distances in the supply chain.

These principles guide the (re)design stage to maximise the chances of a successful safety and sustainability assessment outcome.

The SSbD framework consists of two key phases: the **(re)design phase** and the **assessment phase**, the latter comprising five main steps (Abbate et al., 2025; European Commission JRC, 2023):

- **Step 1 – hazard assessment of the chemical/material (intrinsic properties):**

This step evaluates the inherent hazards of a chemical or material, including toxicity, flammability, carcinogenicity, and environmental persistence. Data from literature, regulatory sources, and predictive models (e.g., QSAR) are used to characterize these hazards. Degradation products are also considered. Hazard classification follows the EU CLP Regulation. The hazard profile guides safer design and substitution decisions early in development.

- **Step 2 – Human health and safety aspects in the chemical/material production and processing phase**

This step evaluates risks to workers and nearby populations during chemical/material production and processing. It identifies exposure pathways such as inhalation, dermal contact, and ingestion, and compares exposure levels to safety thresholds. Risk management measures like engineering controls, personal protective equipment, and process modifications are implemented to reduce exposure and ensure safety during these phases.

- **Step 3 – Human health and environmental aspects in the final application phase**

This step assesses the risks to human health and the environment during the chemical or material's use phase. It evaluates potential exposure routes, such as direct contact and emissions, and compares these to safety limits. Risk management strategies, including design changes and protective measures, are applied to ensure safe use and minimize impacts.

- **Step 4 – Environmental sustainability assessment**

This step uses Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to compare the environmental impacts of a chemical or material against a reference. It highlights improvement opportunities but does not exclude materials solely based on sustainability.

- **Step 5 – Social and economic sustainability assessment**

This step evaluates the broader societal and economic impacts of a chemical or material throughout its lifecycle. It considers factors such as:

- **Social Impacts:** Assessing effects on health, equity, employment, and community well-being.
- **Economic Impacts:** Evaluating aspects like cost-effectiveness, job creation, and market competitiveness.

The assessment aims to ensure that the chemical or material contributes positively to societal welfare and economic development, aligning with sustainability goals. The SSbD framework is iterative, encouraging refinement of assessments as new data emerge. It allows flexibility in applying the steps according to data availability and project needs, aiming to facilitate the development of safer and more sustainable chemicals and materials (European Commission JRC, 2023, 2024).

Based on the results obtained from various studies conducted during the ReLEAF project (characterisation and assessment of secondary raw materials and formulated fertilisers; Techno-economic assessment; Environmental life cycle assessment of production; Social life-cycle assessment, etc.), a compilation of SSbD guidelines will be developed and reported in **D6.12, titled “SSbD recommendations” (M48 of the project)**.

2.3.2. Assessment methodology

Safe and Sustainable by Design – STEP 1: Hazard Assessment and Prioritisation of Substances in the SSbD Framework

The prioritisation of substances based on their hazards is a critical step in aligning with the European Commission's SSbD framework. This framework, established under Recommendation (EU) 2022/2510 (European Commission, 2022), aims to guide the innovation process for chemicals and materials towards safer and more sustainable alternatives. The JRC of the European Commission has outlined specific criteria to assess and prioritise substances (Abbate et al., 2024), ensuring that the most hazardous are identified and managed effectively. This prioritisation helps avoid regrettable substitutions, guides innovation, minimises environmental and health impacts, supports regulatory compliance, enhances transparency, and facilitates continuous improvement.

The methodology implemented in the present work was based on the SSbD guidance, to group the evaluated substances and materials according with the identified intrinsic hazards.

In Table 2.2 are listed the categories of substances through three main groups according to their human health hazards, environmental hazards, and physical hazards. These categories are divided into specific criteria (H1, H2, and H3) to facilitate a comprehensive assessment of each substance's potential risks:

- **Criterion H1** includes the most harmful substances, such as those with carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, reproductive toxicity, and endocrine disruption properties.
- **Criterion H2** encompasses substances of concern that are not already included in Criterion H1, focusing on chronic toxicity and other significant health and environmental impacts.
- **Criterion H3** covers other hazard classes not part of Criteria H1 and H2, including acute toxicity, skin corrosion, and various physical hazards like flammability and explosiveness.

These criteria are designed to ensure a thorough evaluation of substances, considering their potential impacts on human health, the environment, and physical safety. By systematically applying these criteria, the SSbD framework supports the development of safer and more sustainable chemicals and materials throughout their lifecycle. The results of the substances categorisation will be shown in Section 3.

The hazard-based criteria in the context of the SSbD should ensure that the most harmful chemicals and materials, as defined by the criteria, are excluded at the early research and development phase of the new chemicals or materials, and that existing chemicals or materials having these properties are substituted. Additionally, the implementation of these criteria will aid the development of products to not contain the most harmful substances (in line with the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS)), and that the substances of concern are substituted as far as possible. Consequently, it can support the identification of a need for a new design (or redesign) for the chemicals and materials under study.

Table 2.2 - Prioritisation of Substances Based on Hazard Criteria in the SSbD Framework.

Group definition	Human health hazards	Environmental hazards	Physical hazards
<p><i>Includes the most harmful substances (according to CSS (EC, 2020a)), including the substances of very high concern (SVHC) according to REACH Art. 57(a-f)20, 21 (EU, 2006). These hazard properties form Criterion H1.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Carcinogenicity Cat. 1A and 1B · Germ cell mutagenicity Cat. 1A and 1B · Reproductive / developmental toxicity Cat. 1A and 1B · Endocrine disruption Cat. 1 (human health) · Respiratory sensitisation Cat 1 · Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (STOT-RE) Cat. 1, including immunotoxicity and neurotoxicity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic / very persistent and very bioaccumulative (PBT/vPvB) · Persistent, mobile and toxic / very persistent and mobile (PMT/vPvM) · Endocrine disruption Cat. 1 (environment) 	<p>_____</p>

Group definition	Human health hazards	Environmental hazards	Physical hazards
<p><i>Includes substances of concern, as described in CSS (EC, 2020a), defined in the Article 2(28) of SPI proposal (EC, 2022b)22 and that are not already included in Criterion H1. These hazard properties form Criterion H2</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Skin sensitisation Cat 1 · Carcinogenicity Cat. 2 · Germ cell mutagenicity Cat. 2 · Reproductive / developmental toxicity Cat. 2 · Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (STOT-RE) Cat. 2 · Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure (STOT-SE) Cat. 1 and 2 · Endocrine disruption Cat. 2 (human health) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Hazardous for the ozone layer · Chronic environmental toxicity (chronic aquatic toxicity) · Endocrine disruption Cat. 2 (environment) 	<p>_____</p>
<p><i>Includes the other hazard classes not part already in Criteria H1 and H2. These hazard properties form Criterion H3.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Acute toxicity · Skin corrosion · Skin irritation · Serious eye damage/eye irritation · Aspiration hazard (Cat. 1) · Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure (STOT-SE) Cat. 3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Acute environmental toxicity (acute aquatic toxicity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Explosives · Flammable gases, liquids and solids · Aerosols · Oxidising gases, liquids, solids · Gases under pressure · Self-reactive · Pyrophoric liquids, solid · Self-heating · In contact with water emits flammable gas · Organic peroxides · Corrosivity · Desensitised explosives

Following the initial screening, hazard identification, and grouping according to the defined criteria, a ranking system is applied to the assessed chemicals and materials. This system enables the determination of relative hazard levels, thereby supporting assessors in integrating the outcomes of the hazard-based assessment into the overall SSbD approach.

In accordance with Step 1 of the SSbD framework, a cut-off criterion is also implemented at this stage. This cut-off serves as decision-support tool to determine whether a given substance or material may proceed within the SSbD process or should be excluded due to its hazard potential. Step 1 acts as a safety barrier that cannot be bypassed. Once a substance fails the initial hazard assessment, it cannot be considered safe by design, even if it shows excellent environmental or sustainability performance in later evaluation steps.

Figure 2.5 - Ranking of chemicals and materials based on the criterion classification (Caldeira et al., 2022).

The methodology used to qualitatively assess the intrinsic hazards of substances, that will be used, or potentially used during the ingredients production for the ReLEAF’s BBFs was based on the information available on ECHA’s website (ECHA, 2025b). This information derived from the dossiers submitted by registrants, in accordance with REACH and CLP regulations. In addition, other recognised sources, such as Threshold Limit Values (TLVs) from the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH) and the IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans, were consulted to support the identification of potential health risks, especially in cases where no occupational or environmental exposure limits are defined under European Union legislation. These sources also contributed to the identification of relevant considerations for the safe and sustainable production of fertilisers.

Research was also conducted on microorganisms with the potential to be used in the ReLEAF project. This investigation focused on identifying potential health hazards, particularly for workers who might handle the microorganisms during the production of ingredients and the formulation of bio-based fertilisers. To achieve this, various sources were consulted, including relevant legislation, such as,

Directive 2000/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 September 2000, which addresses the protection of workers from risks related to exposure to biological agents at work (7th individual directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).

Additionally, information from other recognised organisations, such as EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), EPA (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency), FDA (U.S. Food and Drug Administration), and corresponding suppliers, was utilised to support the hazard analysis.

The results of the assessment conducted on the intrinsic hazards of the chemical substances and microorganisms are presented in Section 3. A comprehensive table was developed, compiling essential information based on the recognised sources and available literature (see Annex section).

The elements included in the table are essential for the clear identification and traceability of each substance and microorganism across the relevant regulatory frameworks and databases. The table comprises the following columns:

1. **Chemical/Material Name:** The common or scientific name of the substance or microorganism.
2. **Molecular Formula:** The chemical formula representing the composition of the substance or microorganism.
3. **CAS Number:** The unique numerical identifier assigned by the Chemical Abstracts Service.
4. **Physical State:** The state of the substance and microorganism at room temperature (solid, liquid, gas).
5. **Hazards and Hazard Pictograms:** Information on the potential hazards associated with the substance or microorganism, derived (primarily) from the CLP Regulation, but also from REACH, and available through the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). CLP provides harmonised classification for certain hazardous substances, agreed at EU level and listed in Annex VI of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008. The harmonisation ensures consistent hazard communication across the EU and serves as a reliable reference in safety assessments. When no harmonised classification exists, manufacturers and importers carry out self-classification based on the substance's intrinsic properties. These classifications are notified to ECHA's Classification and Labelling Inventory, which offers an extensive source of information for identifying and comparing hazard profiles.
6. **Harmonised Classifications:** Legally binding classifications under EU legislation, if available, as included in the CLP Regulation and its amendments.
7. **Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC):** Identification of substances that require additional regulatory attention under the REACH Regulation.
8. **Seveso III Directive:** Information on whether the substance falls under the Seveso III Directive, indicating the need for enhanced safety measures due to its potential to cause major industrial accidents.
9. **IARC Classification:** Information on the carcinogenic potential of the substance as classified by the International Agency for Research on Cancer.
10. **Threshold Limit Values (TLVs)/Occupational Exposure Limits (OELs):** Exposure limits established by international bodies, particularly where specific EU limits are not available.

11. **PNEC (Predicted No-Effect Concentration) Values:** Values relevant for assessing the environmental impact of the substance.
12. **Environmental Hazard Data:** Information on potential ecotoxicological risks.
13. **Health, Safety, and Environmental Exposure Control Measures:** Recommended risk management measures throughout the life cycle of the substance, as detailed in the ECHA registration dossiers or material safety data sheet.
14. **Other relevant applicable regulations:** identification of applicable regulatory frameworks, such as the Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR) ¹, Prior Informed Consent (PIC) Regulation, and EU Ecolabel, WFD - Waste Framework Directive, where relevant.

This table serves as an essential tool for effective risk communication along the supply chain and for the implementation of appropriate safety measures.

Among the substances with potential to be used in the production of BBFs ingredients, several hydrated forms were identified. However, in many cases, these hydrated forms are not adequately classified in terms of hazards in databases such as ECHA, possibly due to insufficient data. Therefore, applying a precautionary principle, both the anhydrous and hydrated forms were assessed. The anhydrous forms were prioritised in the hazard characterisation, based on their structural and the assumption that the presence of water is unlikely to significantly alter the intrinsic hazardous properties of the substances. Classifications from relevant directives, regulations and international organizations were taken into consideration, in line with their respective scopes and purposes.

- SVHC (Substances of Very High Concern under REACH) - SVHC are defined in Article 57 of Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 ("the REACH Regulation"): The classification applies to the substance itself, including its hydrated forms, if the hazardous component remains chemically active. The hydrated forms are often treated the same if they dissociate in water or biological systems, releasing the same ions (e.g., borate from boric acid, zinc from zinc sulphate). In this regulation the following is mentioned: "Each candidate list entry covers both anhydrous and hydrated forms of a substance. The CAS number shown in an entry is typically for the anhydrous form. Hydrated forms of the substance identified by other CAS numbers are still within the scope of the entry." (ECHA, 2025a).
- SEVESO III- Directive 2012/18/EU: The Seveso III Directive focuses on preventing major accidents involving dangerous substances. Annex I of the directive lists categories of substances and specific named substances with threshold quantities that determine the applicability of the directive. The classification is primarily based on the intrinsic hazardous

¹ Ingredients/micronutrients must comply with: Fertilising Products Regulation, Annex III, Part II- Labelling → "The list contains labelling requirements for a given Product Function Category (PFC), and respective subcategories, related to the content of micronutrients boron (B), cobalt (Co), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), molybdenum (Mo), Copper (Cu) and Zinc (Zn). The list is based on Annex III, Part II. The list is not exhaustive – for detailed labelling requirements please refer to the text of Regulation (EU) No 2019/1009."

properties of substances, such as toxicity, flammability, and environmental hazards (European Union, 2012a). While the directive does not explicitly mention hydrated forms, the inclusion of a substance depends on its hazard classification according to the CLP Regulation (Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008). If a hydrated form exhibits the same hazardous properties as its anhydrous counterpart and meets the classification criteria, it might fall under the same category.

- IARC (International Agency for Research on Cancer): The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) evaluates the carcinogenic risks of substances based on available scientific evidence. The monographs specify the exact chemical forms tested. If only the anhydrous form was evaluated, the classification applies strictly to the anhydrous form.
- ACGIH TLVs[®] (American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists): ACGIH set Threshold Limit Values (TLVs) for chemical substances to guide occupational exposure limits. These limits are often based on the concentration of the active element or moiety responsible for toxicity, regardless of the compound's specific form. For instance, exposure limits for soluble cobalt compounds are expressed as "cobalt," encompassing various cobalt-containing substances, both anhydrous and hydrated. In addition, the guidelines mentioned the following: "When converting values for volatile forms of inorganic compounds (e.g., as Fe, as Ni), the molecular weight of the element should be used, not that of the entire compound." (ACGIH, 2025).

Occupational health considerations when using organic wastes for BBFs production

The processing of organic wastes, such as sewage sludge, fish processing residues, mixed food waste, and agri-food by-products, into ingredients for bio-based fertilisers (BBFs) presents a range of occupational health hazards that require proactive management. While these materials offer valuable nutrients, they are also associated with chemical, biological, and physical risks to workers involved in their handling and transformation.

Sewage sludge has been shown to contain elevated levels of heavy metals such as zinc, copper, and cadmium, often due to industrial discharges (F. Rocha et al., 2025). Direct dermal exposure during handling is a primary concern, with potential non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic effects reported. Additionally, exposure to pathogens, endotoxins, and volatile compounds can be a concern, especially during sludge agitation, drying, or composting operations.

Mixed food waste and anaerobically digested residues (ADRs) (Govasmark et al., 2011) from municipal or industrial sources can contain persistent organic pollutants (POPs) antibiotic-resistant bacteria and pathogenic microorganisms. These pose a dual risk of chemical and biological exposure through skin contact, inhalation of aerosols, or accidental ingestion, especially in open handling environments.

Agri-food by-products, depending on their origin and storage, may emit organic dusts and ammonia, which are known irritants. Moreover, poor waste management or delayed processing can enhance the microbial load, raising the likelihood of infection or allergic reactions among workers.

Fish processing waste, while valuable for its nutrient content, may present risks due to high salt concentrations and microplastics (Zhang et al., 2023a). Increased salt concentrations and the presence of and microplastics (Zhang et al., 2023a). Increased salt concentrations and the presence of contaminants from fish processing can lead to respiratory irritation and skin issues during handling, particularly in enclosed or poorly ventilated environments. Moreover, the biological instability of these materials can result in the release of odorous and potentially harmful bioaerosols.

Emerging contaminants, including pharmaceuticals and personal care products, have also been noted in several waste streams. These compounds are not fully removed during pre-treatment processes, and there is a potential to pose unknown risks through low-level exposure (Zhang et al., 2023a).

Given the risks mentioned, it is essential to implement stringent occupational safety protocols during BBFs ingredient production. These should include (International Labour Organisation, 2010):

- Proper personal protective equipment (PPE) such as gloves, masks, and protective clothing;
- Engineering controls, such as, local exhaust ventilation and enclosed processing systems;
- Biological monitoring, where relevant, especially for exposure to bioaerosols and pathogens; Proper PPE to control exposure to biological agents is also recommended.
- Regular risk assessments and hygiene measures to limit ingestion or inhalation of hazardous substances;
- Pre-treatment and quality control of input materials to minimise the presence of contaminants.

These precautions are necessary not only to protect workers but also to ensure the safe and sustainable production of BBFs, aligning with principles of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD).

Occupational health considerations during the use of microorganisms - Fungi, bacteria, etc. - to produce BBFs ingredients

When using microorganisms, particularly in bioreactors, to produce ingredients for bio-based fertilisers (BBFs) from organic wastes, several occupational health risks should be considered. These microorganisms may release bioaerosols or endotoxins that have the potential to pose respiratory or skin hazards to workers. According to a study by Rasmussen et al (2021) and Kontro et al (2022) bioaerosols, including bacteria, fungi, and other microbial agents, may be released during processing, potentially leading to respiratory issues and skin irritation. Additionally, the processing of organic wastes can involve exposure to pathogenic microorganisms, which could increase the risk of infection if safety measures are not followed.

To mitigate these potential risks, it is important to implement safety protocols such as personal protective equipment (PPE), including masks, gloves, and protective clothing. Engineering controls, such as local exhaust ventilation and enclosed processing systems, can help limit exposure to bioaerosols and microorganisms. Biological monitoring might also be necessary, particularly for

exposure to bioaerosols and pathogens. Regular risk assessments and hygiene protocols are essential to ensure safe handling of microbial cultures and reduce the risk of contamination

3. Results

3.1. Literature Review – Main Findings

The results of the literature review carried out within the scope of T5.1. will be described in the next sections from the environmental and occupational risk points of view. Moreover, results of the preliminary qualitative safety assessment will be depicted in Section 3.2.

3.1.1. Scope and Types of LCA Approaches

To identify key concepts that are relevant for the ReLEAF methods framework and environmental concerns associated with BBF production, a bibliometric analysis of the literature sample was conducted. LCA is widely used to evaluate the environmental performance of different products (or services), including fertilizers. When analysing the bibliometric data, namely the words used in the abstract, keywords and titles of the samples assessed (Figure 3.1), a clear connection emerges between the LCA framework and fertilisers, biofertilisers, and organic fertilisers. These keywords are also directly connected with other ones, such as composting and anaerobic digestion, which are probably the main processes used to convert organic wastes into fertilisers in a composting and digestate state. On the other hand, the bibliometric analysis also showed a potential connection between the environmental assessment of BBF with specific environmental impact metrics, namely ecotoxicity, acidification, ozone layer, and greenhouse gases.

Figure 3.2 and Figure 3.3 illustrates the distribution of publications by article type and by the role that the BBFs have in the studies, respectively. The literature search revealed that most publications are research papers, accounting for 95% of the sample, whereas conference papers and book chapters represent only 4% and 1% of the sample, accordingly. Regarding the BBFs' role, they may be produced within different contexts, and likewise, they may be included in the studies for a variety of reasons. Firstly, when the main aim of the study is to produce a BBF, the environmental impacts may be assessed considering BBF(s) as the main product(s). Secondly, they may be covered as a co-product or a by-product of other systems (*e.g.*, energy valorisation of biomass residues or biofuel production in a biorefinery). Finally, the BBFs may be considered only during the application step, when the study focuses on assessing crop(s) production (*e.g.*, tomato production), being often only studied as consumables. In the sample assessed, most of the articles considered the BBF as a by- or co-product (42%), followed by BBF used as an agronomic input (37%), and bio-based fertiliser as a main product (22%).

Figure 3.2 - Division of the collected sample into different types of articles.

Figure 3.3 - Division of the collected sample into different uses of BBFs.

Given the objective of supporting the decision-making associated with ReLEAF BBFs’ production, we focused on the papers assessing the environmental performance of BBFs as the main product. From these articles, Figure 3.4 depicts the different raw materials used for BBFs production by the different authors.

Figure 3.4 - Raw materials considered by the authors in the reviewed sample

After analysing Figure 3.4, it can be concluded that most of the studies (34%) considered animal manure (including in digestate form) as feedstock, followed by microalgae and wastewater, representing about 20% and 15% of the sample, respectively. In addition, several studies (12%) evaluate the production of BBFs from Organic Municipal Solid Wastes (MSW) and Agro-food residues. After this initial screening, a more detailed analysis was conducted focusing exclusively on studies that consider raw materials of particular relevance to the ReLEAF project and its partners. In this context, the papers studying the production of BBFs from (1) animal manure, (2) non-waste bio feedstock, and (3) human urine were excluded for further analysis. In total, 23 sustainability assessment articles were systematically reviewed, paying particular attention to their system boundaries, functional units, and methodologies employed, as summarised in Table 3.1.

Overall, a *cradle-to-gate* approach was followed in most of the research papers analysed. Some of them also considered the use phase of the bio-based fertilisers (application step). Regarding the functional units (FUs), it can be concluded that different types of FUs were used by different authors according to the aim of the study, namely: *i)* the mass of bio-residues being valorised or used as a feedstock (*e.g.*, 1 ton of organic waste, 1 000 kg of garden waste, or 1 m³ of wastewater); *ii)* the amount of BBF produced (*e.g.*, 1 kg of organo-mineral liquid fertiliser or 1 kg of fertiliser); *iii)* and some FUs based on the amount of macro nutrients, such as nitrogen or phosphorus, included in the BBF produced (*e.g.*, 1 kg of N applied to the soil, or *production of 163 g of P*); *iv)* other FUs, associated with agricultural production requiring the BBF application, such as: “the horticultural production of a ton of commercial tomatoes”, 1 ha of cultivated spinach, and 1 ha of wheat/corn cultivated.

Regarding the methodologies used to assess the sustainability of BBFs, some studies have evaluated both the environmental impacts and the economic and techno-economic performance. Additionally, other studies have assessed the socio-economic and social impacts of the production of BBFs. To further explore the behaviour and the environmental performance of different production processes, some articles considered uncertainty and sensitivity analyses, in which different parameters were

varied, *i.e.*, electricity consumption, energy recovery, transport distance, field emissions, nutrients leaching, and use of some consumables like sodium hydroxide.

Regarding the environmental assessment studies, some of the articles made use of well-known software such as SimaPro (Buratti et al., 2015; Keng et al., 2020; Martínez-Blanco et al., 2009), considered well-established databases like EcoInvent (Keng et al., 2020), or performed the environmental assessment using characterisation factors from the literature (Rupawalla et al., 2021). To calculate the impacts of production BBFs on the environment, different impact assessment methods were used, namely, ReCiPe (Arashiro et al., 2018; Bałazińska et al., 2020; J. de S. Castro et al., 2020; J. S. Castro et al., 2023; de Souza et al., 2019; Estévez et al., 2022, 2023; Pereira et al., 2023), CML (Martínez-Blanco et al., 2009; Styles et al., 2018), TRACI ((Ishii & Boyer, 2015; Keng et al., 2020), IMPACT 2002+ (Buratti et al., 2015), ILCD (ten Hoeve et al., 2019), and IChemE metrics (Fernández-Delgado et al., 2022).

Table 3.1 - Aim, methodologies and main considerations of the studies analysed² (G2G = Gate-to-Gate, Cr2G = Cradle-to-Gate, Cr2Gr=Cradle-to-Grave, G2Gr=Gate-to-Grave).

Reference	Aim	Type(s) of Waste(s)	System boundaries				Functional Unit	Methodologies
			G2G	Cr2G	Cr2Gr	G2Gr		
(Martínez-Blanco et al., 2009)	Evaluate the agricultural and environmental viability of compost in tomato crops in Mediterranean areas. Compare the environmental impacts of compost vs. mineral fertilisers.	Organic MSW		x*			“the horticultural production of a ton of commercial tomatoes.”	Environmental assessment: LCA
(Ishii & Boyer, 2015)	Assess the environmental and economic impacts of managing nitrogen and phosphorus in urine through source separation and struvite precipitation vs. centralised wastewater treatment.	Wastewater		x			“conveyance, storage, and nutrient management of 1920 m ³ of urine.”	Environmental assessment: LCA Economic analysis
(Buratti et al., 2015)	Assess the environmental effects of two ways to manage organic waste in Umbria, Italy. Give information to support strategic decisions and optimisation of the organic waste management system.	Organic MSW		x			1 ton of Organic Fraction (waste).	Environmental assessment: LCA Sensitivity analysis
(Styles et al., 2018)	Evaluate traditional Liquid Digestate (LD) management against Digestate Biofertiliser (DBF) production and usage concerning resource efficiency and environmental effects.	Food Waste				x	1 m ³ of liquid digestate from food waste anaerobic digestion plant.	Environmental assessment: LCA Uncertainty analysis
(Arashiro et al., 2018)	Assess the possible environmental effects linked to High-rate Algal Pounds (HRAP) systems in wastewater treatment while considering two strategies for resource recovery.	Wastewater Microalgae			x		1 m ³ of processed water.	Environmental assessment: LCA
(de Souza et al., 2019)	Assess the effects of producing, harvesting, and using microalgae biomass from meat processing industry effluent as nitrogen fertiliser for cultivating millet.	Microalgae		x*			1 kg of N applied to the soil.	Environmental assessment: LCA
(ten Hoeve et al., 2019)	Compare the environmental performance of different garden waste management options.	Garden Waste		x*			1 000 kg of garden waste generated.	Environmental assessment: LCA

² * Use phase included.

Reference	Aim	Type(s) of Waste(s)	System boundaries				Functional Unit	Methodologies
			G2G	Cr2G	Cr2Gr	G2Gr		
	Assess the impact of (1) removing the woody fraction before composting, and (2) reducing the composting time before land application.							
(J. de S. Castro et al., 2020)	Evaluate the environmental effects of producing a microalgae biomass-derived phosphate biofertiliser in comparison to triple superphosphate (TSP).	Microalgae		x			“the production of 163 g of P”.	Environmental assessment: LCA Sensitivity analysis
(Bałazińska et al., 2020)	Determine the environmental impact of the developed organic-mineral fertiliser production method. Compare and choose the most environmentally friendly fertiliser among the alternatives considered.	Wastewater Sewage sludge		x			1 Mg of fertilizer produced. 1 kg of fertilizer (comparison analysis)	Environmental assessment: LCA
(Keng et al., 2020)	Demonstrate the feasibility of a community-scale composting system for food waste.	Garden Waste Food Waste		x			“the continuous treatment of 200 kg/day of organic wastes.”	Environmental assessment: LCA
(González-Cencerrado et al., 2020)	Evaluate the environmental benefits of biochar-based fertilisers compared to traditional fertilisers through nitrogen savings.	Agro-food Wastes					1 ha of wheat/corn cultivated.	Environmental assessment: LCA
(Rupawalla et al., 2021)	Assess the effects of algae fertiliser (AF), synthetic nitrogen fertiliser (SF), and various combinations of both on crop growth, quality, nutrient losses, and specific soil properties. Perform a comprehensive "triple bottom line" techno-economic and life-cycle analysis using the findings from the initial phase of the study.	Microalgae		x*			1 kg of N ⁻¹ Fertilise dose in m ⁻² . yr ⁻¹	Tecno-economic analysis Environmental assessment: LCA
(He et al., 2021)	Assess the environmental impacts connected to the recycling of Lignocellulose Wastes (LCWs) by raising mealworms and composting the resulting frass.	Agriculture Waste		x			1 kg LCWs treatment.	Environmental assessment: LCA
(Yoshikawa et al., 2021)	Assess the environmental, and socio-economic impacts of different food waste treatment and farming systems.	Food Waste		x*			1 kg of spinach produced. 1 ha of cultivated spinach.	Environmental assessment: LCA Socio-economic analysis Sensitivity analysis
(Estévez et al., 2022)	Assess the environmental impact of systems that combine wastewater management with agricultural practices.	Wastewater		x*			1 m ² of urban garden.	Environmental assessment: LCA

Reference	Aim	Type(s) of Waste(s)	System boundaries				Functional Unit	Methodologies
			G2G	Cr2G	Cr2Gr	G2Gr		
								Economic analysis
(Fernández-Delgado et al., 2022)	Evaluate different technologies (conventional and microwave extraction) using water and alkaline solutions to recover carbon and nitrogen from municipal waste compost and produce a liquid organo-mineral fertiliser. Assess the technical, economic, and environmental feasibility of the different scenarios.	Organic MWS		x			1 kg of organo-mineral liquid fertiliser. 1 l of organo-mineral liquid fertiliser.	Environmental assessment: LCA Economic analysis
(J. S. Castro et al., 2023)	Evaluate the environmental and economic performance of commercially producing key products from microalgae Investigate and compare the environmental impacts associated with utilising microalgae biomass through hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC) in the production of solid biofuel and biofertiliser	Microalgae		x			Effluent flow rate of 12.5 m ³ /h.	Environmental assessment: LCA Economic analysis
(Estévez et al., 2023)	Assess and compare the potential environmental impacts of various decentralised wastewater treatment methods, with a primary focus on the recovery of phosphorus nutrients within the system.	Wastewater		x			kg of P ₂ O ₅ (Phosphorus Pentoxide).	Environmental assessment: LCA
(Pereira et al., 2023)	Analyse the environmental viability of manufacturing pelletised organomineral fertiliser and its potential use as biofertilizer for corn cultivation. Explore and compare the environmental burdens associated with the production of biofertilisers vs. conventional ones.	Microalgae		x*			1 kg of corn.	Environmental assessment: LCA Uncertainty analysis
(Josa & Garfí, 2023)	Evaluate the social impacts associated with the life cycle stages of resource recovery from microalgae grown in two different types of wastewater. Identify opportunities and challenges for large-scale implementation.	Wastewater Microalgae		x*			1 m ³ of water.	Social Life Cycle Assessment
(Suprihatin et al., 2023)	Assess the environmental burden of processing crab shells (CS) into chitosan, liquid organic fertiliser, and animal feed.	Fish Residues		x			1 kg of CS.	Environmental assessment: LCA
(Mulya et al., 2024)	Evaluate the emissions of the upstream processes of biofertilizer, which includes cultivated bacteria.	Bacteria		x			1 L of liquid biofertilizer produced. 1 kg of fertiliser.	Environmental assessment: LCA

Reference	Aim	Type(s) of Waste(s)	System boundaries				Functional Unit	Methodologies
			G2G	Cr2G	Cr2Gr	G2Gr		
(Iglesias et al., 2025)	Quantify the environmental burdens of using mushroom substrate (SMS) as a soil improver. Compare the results with a non-renewable alternative.	Agro-food wastes.			x		1 ton of SMS.	Environmental assessment: LCA Economic analysis

In environmental impact assessment, particularly in the context of LCA, midpoint and endpoint indicators represent different stages in the cause-effect chain of environmental damage. Midpoint indicators focus on impacts in an early stage, while endpoint indicators provide a more holistic view of long-term environmental consequences, aggregating the effects on human health, ecosystem quality, and resource scarcity, and generally incorporating higher uncertainty. Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6 depict the relative share of papers found assessing different impact categories at the midpoint and endpoint, respectively. As it can be observed, Global Warming potential (GWP) is the most used impact category, being considered by 100% of the authors. Nevertheless, when evaluating the environmental impacts of producing BBFs from different raw materials (wastes), other impact categories seem to be meaningful. For example, categories such as Ozone depletion (OD), Eutrophication (including freshwater and marine; EUT-M, EUT-F), Terrestrial acidification (Acid-T) were used by more than 30% of the studies.

Figure 3.5- Number of papers and midpoints considered during the environmental assessment studies (abbreviations are explained in the glossary).

Focusing on the endpoints (Figure 3.6), 5 out of 23 of the studies assessed the environmental impacts by considering the endpoints after evaluating the midpoints.

Figure 3.6 - Number of papers and endpoints considered during the environmental assessment studies (abbreviations are explained in the glossary).

Some studies also considered the assessment of a single score (Bałazińska et al., 2020; J. S. Castro et al., 2023; Estévez et al., 2022; González-Cencerrado et al., 2020; Iglesias et al., 2025; Pereira et al., 2023).

3.1.2. Scope of socioeconomic Assessments

Considering the economic analysis, different KPIs were used by the authors, namely, total costs (Ishii & Boyer, 2015), CAPEX (Capital Expenditures) and OPEX (Operational Expenditures) (Estévez et al., 2022), profit and minimum selling price (Fernández-Delgado et al., 2022), Net Present Value (NPV) (Fernández-Delgado et al., 2022; Iglesias et al., 2025), construction/acquisition costs, and operational costs (J. S. Castro et al., 2023).

Regarding the social and socioeconomic studies, different indicators were considered. For example, in their S-LCA, Josa and Garfí, (2023) assess the following social impacts associated with different stakeholders (*i.e.*, workers, consumers, local communities, value chain actors, and society): (a) Health and Safety (for workers and consumers), (b) Working Conditions, (c) Quality and Performance, (d) Acceptability, (e) Socioeconomic Repercussions, (f) Technological Development, (g) Liveability, (h) Promotion of social, (i) Responsibility (value chain actors only), and (j) Public commitment to sustainability issues (society only). On the other hand, Yoshikawa et al., (2021) assessed the socioeconomic impacts of the farming systems by evaluating the Gross value added, Life cycle costs, and Employment inducement.

3.1.3. Summaries of Studies Reviewed in-depth

Table 3.2 depicts the scenarios, main results and limitations of the studies analysed. A deeper examination of this table can support the following conclusions. In general, the environmental performance of the BBFs studied varied widely according to the scenarios considered. For example, the bio-based fertilisers may reduce the carbon footprint, acidification, and eutrophication impacts

when compared with conventional fertilisers. Nevertheless, their benefits are highly dependent on the production route, energy sources, and other characteristics like the application context. On the other hand, other BBFs (*e.g.*, microalgae-based and compost from woody materials) may have higher potential environmental impacts because of the use of energy-intensive processes and emissions during treatment and their application.

Table 3.2 - Scope of application of the BBFs, limitations, and main results of the studies assessed.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
(Martínez-Blanco et al., 2009)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compost (C). Compost with mineral fertiliser (C + M). Mineral fertiliser (M). 	Tomato Cultivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario C (without system expansion) has the highest impacts (33% to 95% higher than Scenario M), mainly due to gas emissions and energy use in composting, accounting for 53% to 98% of total burdens. With system expansion and avoided burdens, Scenario C shows similar or lower impacts than M, except in the PO category, where it has 32 times more impacts due to compost production. The use of organic fertiliser does not negatively affect tomato crop yields or quality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efforts must focus on optimising production processes, improving exhaust gas treatment, and reducing energy use to improve compost treatment. Developing indicators for local impacts in Mediterranean areas, including erosion and water consumption, is essential. Specific data on the environmental effects of organic waste in landfills is also needed for better evaluation.
(Ishii & Boyer, 2015)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Baseline: Centralised wastewater treatment (A). Urine collection, storage, struvite precipitation with MgO, and centralised wastewater treatment (B). Urine collection, storage, struvite precipitation with MgO and Na₃PO₄, and centralised wastewater treatment (C). 	-	<p><u>Economic results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The cost ranking for each scenario is as follows: Scenario B > Scenario A > Scenario C, with about a 13% difference between B and C. Costs for toilets, pipes, storage tanks, and chemicals in Scenarios B and C are offset by savings from less potable water usage, lower wastewater treatment costs, and revenue from struvite. Although Scenario C has the lowest total cost, it requires significant chemical inputs for phosphorus and nitrogen recovery, raising environmental and quality concerns. <p><u>Environmental results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario C has the highest environmental impacts, followed by Scenario A, then Scenario B, with the least impact (best option). In Scenario A, high impacts are due to the electricity used for treating urine and flush water. A key issue is the eutrophication impact from treated wastewater that contains nitrogen and phosphorus. Scenario B also contributes to eutrophication due to treated urine discharge. Most of the environmental impacts are caused by urine storage materials, urine conveyance pipes, and magnesium oxide for struvite precipitation. The main benefit of this scenario is the nutrient recycling related to phosphorus. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct air emissions from centralised wastewater treatment processes, urine storage, or struvite precipitation (e.g., CO₂, N₂O, NH₃) were not included. The results highlight the need to explore alternative reagents for precipitation that could replace high-quality magnesium and phosphorus sources, such as groundwater with high hardness, lime residuals, seawater, and other potential alternatives like wood ash and bittern. Investigating other nitrogen recovery and disinfection methods for source-separated urine beyond struvite precipitation and storage is needed.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario C's impacts are mainly due to the trisodium phosphate and magnesium oxide consumed during struvite production. <p><u>Sensitivity analysis results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The environmental impacts are generally ranked Scenario C > Scenario A > Scenario B. The only exception was when assuming minimum nitrogen content in urine, where Scenarios A and C showed similar burdens regarding ozone depletion, smog, and eutrophication. Scenario C is especially sensitive to nitrogen content, while Scenario B is most affected by urine storage time. In Scenario A, electricity use for treatment is the primary factor impacting environmental burdens. 	
(Buratti et al., 2015)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Undifferentiated waste collection, bio-stabilisation of the organic fraction, and landfill disposal (1). Source-separated organic waste collection, and composting (2). 	-	<p><u>Midpoint results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario 1 outperformed Scenario 2 in 10 out of 15 impact categories, while Scenario 2 had lower impacts on carcinogens, land occupation, aquatic eutrophication, global warming, and mineral extraction midpoints. <p><u>Endpoint results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario 2 only presented the best environmental performance in the climate change damage category. Human health impacts mainly arose from emissions in both scenarios. Ecosystem quality was affected by ammonia emissions in both scenarios, with Scenario 1 also having considerable impacts from aluminium emissions. Landfill greenhouse gas emissions were significant in Scenario 1, while Scenario 2's impacts were linked to bio-stabilisation. The resource endpoint was driven by fossil fuel use in Scenario 1 and electricity consumption in Scenario 2. <p><u>Sensitivity analysis results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Including carbon sequestration in landfills and composting reduced greenhouse gas emissions for both scenarios. Improved biogas collection efficiency also benefited Scenario 1. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research is needed on biogas collection efficiency and fugitive emissions from organic waste landfilling.
(Styles et al., 2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Four scenarios for conventional liquid digestate (LD): LD-1 (Optimum), LD-2 (Good), 	Calculations (e.g., nutrient concentration and fertiliser	<p><u>Environmental results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The production and use of DBF resulted in total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions between less than 1 kg CO₂ equivalent (DBF-1) and 12,5 kg CO₂-eq (DBF-3) per cubic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research is needed on farmers' digestate management practices to estimate emissions and fertiliser substitution benefits accurately.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
	<p>LD-3 (Default), and LD-4 (Worst).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Three scenarios of the digestate biofertilizer (DBF): DBF-1 (Optimum), DBF-2 (Default), and DBF-3 (Worst). ▪ The production of DBF comprises struvite precipitation, crystallised precipitation of P, ammonia air-stripping, and crystallisation of N. 	<p>replacement) were made using MANNER-NPK software.</p>	<p>meter of processed LD, compared to 5 to 34 kg CO₂-eq for conventional LD management. DBF reduces GHG emissions by minimising direct and indirect N₂O and CH₄ emissions from digestate storage and application, potentially reducing the total GHG from food waste digestion by 8%.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Acidification impacts are mainly obtained due to the NH₃ emissions, ranging from 0,7 to 4,3 kg SO₂ equivalent per cubic meter of LD based on management practices. Upgrading LD to DBF can reduce the acidification burden by up to 73%. ▪ Eutrophication patterns are similar, with DBF extraction reducing this burden by 85%. ▪ Overall, upgrading LD to DBF addresses significant environmental issues in anaerobic digestion (AD) systems. ▪ Key benefits of biofertiliser include reduced NH₃ emissions and improved resource conservation. <p><u>Uncertainty analysis results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Transport and upstream impacts were varied by ±20% in the LD scenarios to account for uncertainty. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A detailed economic analysis of DBF vs. better digestate management is necessary to identify cost-effective operation contexts. ▪ Investment in struvite extraction and ammonia stripping technologies (commercial scale) should be prioritised to increase efficiency and reduce costs. ▪ Policies should promote pollution-mitigating technologies like biofertiliser extraction through measures such as pollution taxes or tighter regulations on residue management.
<p>(Arashiro et al., 2018)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ HRAP system with biomass valorisation – biogas production (1). ▪ HRAP system with reused biomass – biofertilizer production (2). ▪ Conventional small-sized system with sludge incineration (3). 	<p>Agricultural Fields</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Scenario 1 performed better in Climate Change, Ozone Depletion, and Fossil Depletion due to the biogas energy offset. ▪ Scenario 2 is the best setup in Freshwater Eutrophication, Marine Eutrophication, and Terrestrial Acidification due to improved nutrient recovery and lower emissions. ▪ HRAP systems had lower impacts than the activated sludge system (scenario 3) in 6 out of 11 categories. ▪ Scenario 2 had higher nutrient recovery efficiency, making it suitable for warmer climates. On the other hand, scenario 1 showed seasonal performance variations, while scenario 2 was more stable throughout the year. Scenario 3 had higher overall impacts from energy consumption, but lower metal depletion impacts due to a smaller surface area needed. ▪ HRAP with biofertiliser production was more economically viable than with biogas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Investment in struvite extraction and ammonia stripping is needed for efficiency and cost reduction. ▪ Further research on microalgal production variability and stability is necessary. ▪ The heavy metal content in biofertilisers and methods for reducing ammonia emissions from HRAP require more study.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
(de Souza et al., 2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biofertiliser production and application (1). Conventional urea fertiliser application (2). 	Agricultural Fields	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario 1: The production phase had the highest environmental impact, mainly in the climate change category, due to high electricity usage and NaOH for biomass harvesting. On the other hand, lower impacts on freshwater eutrophication and ecotoxicity were noted since effluent served as a nutrient source for microalgae growth. Scenario 1 had higher impacts than scenario 2 in most categories, especially climate change, due to its energy-intensive production. Scenario 1 showed lower terrestrial acidification (0,43 kg SO₂-eq vs. 0,53 kg SO₂-eq for urea) from reduced ammonia volatilisation and nitrogen losses. Net greenhouse gas emissions from soil were lower with biofertiliser scenario due to decreased N₂O emissions, despite higher CO₂ emissions during organic matter degradation. Transitioning to photovoltaic energy could reduce climate change impacts by 73% and particulate matter formation by 56%. Using nitrogen-rich effluent could decrease the cultivation cycles needed to produce 1 kg of nitrogen, reducing electricity and chemical input impacts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low productivity due to competition with microorganisms suggests a need for optimised conditions. Reducing HRAP system energy requirements is essential, potentially through improved strategies or technologies. Lowering NaOH usage could reduce impacts during harvesting. An Environmental Compensation Framework could improve the economic competitiveness of biofertilisers. The study's small-scale data may not reflect larger-scale challenges. Thus, further research is needed to validate the findings.
(ten Hoeve et al., 2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mature compost with woody fraction (MCIW). Mature compost without woody fraction (MCWW). Immature compost without woody fraction (ICWW). Garden waste with woody fraction (GWIW). Garden waste without woody fraction (GWWW). 	Land Application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composting garden waste can lead to environmental impacts that are comparable to or greater than those of no treatment before land application. Even with a 10% reduction in NH₃ emissions, composting scenarios exhibited higher impacts for terrestrial eutrophication and acidification than scenarios using fresh garden waste. In the marine eutrophication category, performance varies by soil type and precipitation. Fresh garden waste consistently performed better, while immature compost without woody material and mature compost with woody material performed worst. Removing the woody fraction from compost or fresh garden waste positively impacted climate change impacts via fossil energy substitution. Scenarios involving woody fractions resulted in the highest levels of carbon sequestration and nitrogen emissions after application. Toxicity potential remained almost unchanged with garden waste treatment, but removing woody material slightly lowered toxicity due to reduced metal content. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Toxicity assessments should be interpreted cautiously, as USEtox characterisation factors may be overestimated. Other unaccounted factors, such as seedbed establishment issues and phytotoxic effects, may inhibit the practicality of direct garden waste application. Farmers face challenges with direct garden waste application, including reduced crop yields in the first year and other agronomic factors. However, long-term benefits include improved soil fertility and water retention due to increased organic matter. Future studies should model long-term emissions based on soil type and precipitation conditions.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
(J. de S. Castro et al., 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biofertiliser produced based on drying and granulation processes (A). ▪ Conventional TSP fertiliser (B). 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Results were sensitive to the type of energy used (fossil vs. renewable) and to soil and climate conditions. <p><u>Environmental results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The microalgae biofertiliser (A) exhibited a more environmental impact than TSP across all categories, particularly in terrestrial ecotoxicity (87,33% higher) and climate change (75,28% higher). ▪ Granulation was the process that contributed the most to environmental impacts, except for climate change and terrestrial ecotoxicity, due to the energy required for biofertiliser production and TSP manufacturing. ▪ In the climate change category, TSP inputs were close. Nevertheless, the biofertiliser was about 75% more impactful due to energy consumption during biomass production. ▪ Although using effluent for cultivation reduced some environmental impacts, it was not sufficient to offset the overall negative effects. <p><u>Sensitivity analysis results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Changing the energy source negatively impacted freshwater eutrophication but led to significant reductions in climate change effects (approximately 47%). However, the biofertiliser remained more impactful than conventional fertilisers. ▪ The biofertiliser without NaOH was less impactful compared to when NaOH was used, though still not less than TSP. ▪ The best scenario for BBF involved photovoltaic panels, biomass concentration without NaOH, and natural drying. Although this significantly reduced environmental impacts, TSP proved to be more environmentally friendly. ▪ TSP combined with 12% microalgae biomass fertiliser achieved a higher phosphorus recovery rate, offering potential long-term environmental benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ There is a need for refined phosphorus recovery methods through microalgae cultivation that minimise environmental impacts. ▪ Emphasising strategies that lower energy consumption is critical, as energy use is a key contributor to environmental impacts. ▪ More research is needed regarding coagulant alternatives to NaOH, as they can lead to adverse outcomes such as metal bioaccumulation. ▪ Sustainable energy sources and alternative drying methods should be explored, with future studies extending the scale and duration of experiments to better assess the technical, economic, and environmental viability of using microalgae biomass with mineral fertilisers.
(Bałazińska et al., 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Four different mineral-organic fertilisers were studied (<i>i.e.</i>, Fertiliser 1, 2, 3, and 4). 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fertiliser 3 had the worst environmental performance, while fertiliser 4 had the lowest environmental impacts. ▪ The use of ammonium carbonate in product four improved nitrogen content but significantly increased eutrophication impact. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Future optimisation may involve removing dolomite flour due to its energy-intensive grinding process.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The most environmentally friendly product should include sewage sludge, cellulose, dolomite flour, and gypsum. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comparisons with literature fertilisers are preliminary and require careful analysis because different assumptions may be considered.
(Keng et al., 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BBF resulting from the composting process (<i>i.e.</i>, preparation, feeding, control during composting, curing, and finishing). 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The waste collection phase is identified as having the highest number of critical concerns, particularly due to the transportation of food waste from the cafeteria to the composting site, as well as the collection of landscaping waste using trucks. Transitioning from disposal methods (like landfilling) to composting, along with replacing chemical fertilisers with compost, had significantly mitigated environmental impacts, especially concerning global warming, ecotoxicity, eutrophication, and fossil fuel depletion. The composting process primarily contributes to concerns regarding ecotoxicity, non-carcinogenic substances, carcinogenic substances, and eutrophication. Using composting as a treatment method instead of landfilling has resulted in substantial reductions of 46% in ecotoxicity, 22,7% in non-carcinogenic and 22,2% in carcinogenic impacts, 20,9% in eutrophication, and 9,7% in global warming. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conducting a supply chain analysis can support policy formulation and promote the broader adoption of sustainable bio-waste treatment in communities and agricultural sectors. An optimisation model could be developed to identify the most effective waste management methods, assess scalability and production capacity, and evaluate the economic performance of the entire waste management supply chain, enabling a circular economy approach.
(González-Cencerrado et al., 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic fertiliser (1). Four conventional alternatives considered: Urea (2), Ammonium Sulphate (3), Ammonium Nitrate (4), and Diammonium Phosphate (5). 	Pot Trials of Wheat and Corn.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ammonium nitrate is a hotspot mainly associated with aquatic eutrophication, while terrestrial eutrophication potential concerns the other fertilisers. Terrestrial eutrophication potential results are verified due to NH₃ volatilisation, whereas climate change potential is connected to N₂O emissions. Aquatic eutrophication is influenced by both NH₃ volatilisation and NO₃ leaching. The EcoX assessment shows that urea has the highest environmental impacts for both crops. Ammonium nitrate and biochar-based fertilisers (organic fertiliser) have similar risks for wheat, while biochar performs better for corn at higher fertiliser application rates. Biochar-based fertilisers achieve a 63,42% reduction in mineral nitrogen compared to urea, indicating they are a promising and cost-effective option to reduce nitrogen contamination. 	
(Rupawalla et al., 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synthetic N-fertiliser (SF) – (1). 	Pot Trials of Spinach.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overall, microalgae demonstrate strong potential for nutrient recycling, enhancing the resilience and sustainability of food production systems. Scenarios 2–4 significantly reduced CO₂ emissions but did not improve freshwater use, land use, embodied energy, or crop yield. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fertiliser formulation processes like pelletisation and coating were not included. Carbon and nitrogen emissions from microbial activity were outside the study's boundaries.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fertiliser from freshwater algae (AF) – (2). Mix with the ratio 75:25 of freshwater AF: SF (3). Mix with the ratio 75:25 of wastewater AF: SF (4). 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On a per square meter per year basis, scenarios 2–4 showed benefits in CO₂ emissions reductions, nitrogen loss, and soil and crop quality (scenarios 3 and 4). However, they did not enhance freshwater use, embodied energy, or crop yield. Scenario 1 performed best for nitrogen per kg, while Scenario 4 outperformed when considering a unit per square meter per year. AF-N had the best environmental performance, but it was negatively affected by its social and economic metrics. Scenario 2 had the best environmental performance, followed by scenario 4, demonstrating advantages over scenario 1. Economic performance for scenarios 3 and 4 improved (compared to scenario 1) due to better crop quality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Additional benefits of algae, such as acting as bio-stimulants and providing plant growth-promoting hormones and defences, were not considered in this analysis.
(He et al., 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Three composting scenarios using different feedstocks for mealworms: Rice Straw (A), Corn Straw (B), and conventional feedstock (C). 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The environmental impacts of the three scenarios were ranked as C < A < B for all categories except photochemical oxidation, indicating lower environmental impacts from rice straw cultivating and composting compared to corn straw. Scenario A had a lower environmental impact than scenario B for most categories, suggesting that using frass from rice straw-fed mealworms is an eco-friendly practice. The main environmental hotspots were electricity consumption, followed by CO₂ emissions during cultivating and composting, while the impact of N₂O on global warming potential was minimal. Lower electricity use led to a reduced frass conversion rate. Meaningful CO₂ emission variations were observed during composting, with emissions of 21,73 kg, 20,77 kg, and 21,83 kg for scenarios A, B, and C, respectively. Sensitivity analysis revealed that variations in most factors had negligible effects, highlighting minimal influence from elements other than P fertiliser on soil organic matter. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Future research should focus on better control of gaseous emissions to mitigate environmental risks and global warming potential. A key challenge is to enhance mealworms' lignocellulosic crop waste consumption rate while reducing disposal impacts. Additional studies on mealworms' metabolic pathways and regulatory mechanisms are necessary for further development.
(Yoshikawa et al., 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incineration (conventional) – (1). On-site composting (2). Central composting (3). 	Spinach Cultivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-site centralised composting reduces landfill waste and overall environmental impact. However, there is a trade-off between reducing landfill waste and increasing GHGs emissions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further studies should quantify the substitution effect of compost on reducing chemical fertiliser use, which was not addressed in this study.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composting is environmentally and socio-economically viable compared to conventional organic farming. Reducing the amount or emission factor of electricity used is critical to enhancing environmental competitiveness compared to conventional systems. 	
(Estévez et al., 2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decentralised baseline scenario (DBS). Vacuum toilet (energy reduction scenario) – (DRS). Energy supplied by PV cells (DSS). Mix between DSS and DRS scenarios – (DJS). Centralised scenario (CS). 	Land application in a residential area to cultivate peppers, cabbages, carrots, and bush beans.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The hybrid scenario (DBS) results in lower total environmental impacts than the centralised scenario. The most significant reduction occurs in the fossil resource scarcity category (74,8%), followed by terrestrial ecotoxicity (70,1%), marine ecotoxicity (66,8%), and freshwater ecotoxicity (66,7%). The production and application of fertilisers for crops, along with the use of machinery, have meaningful impacts on the environment. The main difference in environmental performance of DBS and CS results from the biofertiliser production process at the wastewater treatment facility, which contributes the most for the burdens in most categories (80–98%). The Net Present Value (NPV) for the decentralised facility in the DBS scenario shows a lack of financial sustainability in wastewater management. The NPV of this scenario is 255,85 €·person⁻¹, which mirrors previous studies but illustrates that current treatment fees do not cover the necessary investment. The sensitivity analysis revealed that the centralised scenario scores 79,75 mPt, significantly higher than innovative systems. All scenarios exhibit improvements over conventional systems, highlighting the potential for decentralised toilet systems and biowaste segregation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research is needed to improve the environmental efficiency of vacuum toilets, as notable differences in electricity demand and water usage per flush have been identified.
(Fernández-Delgado et al., 2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solid/liquid extraction using conventional technique with Water (Scenario 1: CSE-Water), and KOH solution (Scenario 2: CSE-KOH). Solid/liquid extraction using microwave-assisted technique with water (Scenario 3: MAE-Water), 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Previous research shows higher concentrations of humic acids when extraction occurs under alkaline conditions. In MAE scenarios, the solid-to-liquid (S/L) ratio indicates that the MAE-KOH scenario (30% w/v) handles more mass compared to the MAE-Water scenario (40% w/v). MAE scenarios consumed more energy per kg of product than CSE scenarios, mainly due to differences in operating temperatures. Water-based extractions have more environmental impacts than CSE and MAE methods using KOH. The CSE scenario with alkaline solvent is the most favourable for scaling up. 	

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
	and KOH solution (Scenario 4: MAE-KOH).		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The total investment cost for CSE scenarios range from €1,1 million to €1,4 million, while MAE scenarios range from €3,7 million to €4,2 million. CSE scenarios, especially CSE-KOH, are more economically viable due to lower production costs. Alkaline extraction increases raw material expenses, while water-based processes benefit from recycling. The sensitivity analysis shows the minimum selling price for alkaline extraction is around €1 per litre, compared to over €4 for water-based extraction. 	
(J. S. Castro et al., 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solid biofuel production (1). Biofertiliser production (2). 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Characterisation results showed that scenario 1 had significantly higher environmental impact than scenario 2, especially in freshwater eutrophication (nearly 7 times higher), fossil resource scarcity (4,2 times higher), global warming, and marine ecotoxicity (approximately 2,7 times higher for both). The cultivation (in HRAP) and mechanical dewatering (in filter press) stages accounted for most of the environmental impacts across scenarios 1 and 2, contributing to 45%-50% and 35%-50% of them, respectively. The main environmental hotspots of the biofertiliser production were electricity and CO₂. Damage assessment (endpoints) confirmed higher environmental damages in scenario 1 than scenario 2, supporting the conclusion that biofertiliser has better environmental performance. The cost of producing biofertiliser (2) is slightly lower than that of hydrochar (1), with a 3% difference. Scenario 2 is the most economically viable option for HTC valorisation, while scenario 1 is estimated to be unfeasible due to negative NPV and lack of payback within 30 years. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Future studies should explore microalgae valorisation pathways and mitigate environmental impacts. Unaccounted emissions during the hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC) stage and the scale of bench experiments limit findings. Optimising electricity usage in HRAPs and improving biomass productivity could help reduce operational costs. Future research should focus on larger-scale economic and environmental modelling and incorporate labour and maintenance costs for a more realistic financial assessment.
(Estévez et al., 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decentralised treatment for pellet BBF production (HC). Hybrid decentralised treatment process for a 	-	<p><u>Water line results (HC, SC, GC scenarios):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The SC configuration is the most effective, but not fully decentralised. Higher phosphorus recovery leads to lower environmental impacts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Future LCA studies should compare wastewater treatment facilities while considering energy decarbonisation, energy-consumption efficiencies, and a stronger focus on circular economy principles.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ small residential area (SC). ▪ Decentralised system for P recovery in struvite form (GC). ▪ Three scenarios for combined systems (centralised and decentralised): Johkasou-Senboku-Configuration (JSC), Johkasou-AshDec-Configuration (JAC), and Johkasou-Lysogest-Configuration (JLC). 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The GC configuration performs poorly when sludge is considered waste, but recovering nutrients significantly decreases the impact per kg of P₂O₅ by over 90% in many categories, surpassing HC and SC in several areas. ▪ SC's main hotspots were the potable water (39–46%) and grey water treatment (27–33%), influenced by electricity use. ▪ HC's impacts arise mainly due to the electricity used for pumping and sodium hydroxide used for production (27–49% and 39–58%), with significant contributions from aeration emissions for the global warming potential. This impact category is also very influenced (about 71%) by the N₂, CO₂ and N₂O emissions. <p><u>Sludge line results (JAC, JLC, JSC scenarios):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ JSC has the highest environmental impact, while JAC is the most efficient due to better phosphorus recovery. ▪ JSC's environmental performance is affected by membrane filtration processes, whereas dewatering and incineration were most important for JAC. ▪ Impacts from centralised processes were verified mostly because of raw sludge handling. 	
(Pereira et al., 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Five scenarios of BBF (pellet shape) according to the percentage of microalgae biomass (MB): 5% (C1), 15% (C2), 30% (C3), 40% (C4), and 50% (C5). ▪ Conventional scenario: Urea (U). ▪ Optimised scenario (C2-O). 	Corn Cultivation (Greenhouse)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The LCA results showed that increasing MB in fertiliser typically raised environmental impacts, with water consumption as the exception. The combined MB and Urea fertiliser had a lower impact than Urea alone. ▪ Energy consumption was highest during microalgae cultivation and pellet production, ranging from 6,54 to 107,80 Wh. The cultivation phase accounted for 45,46% to 82,59% of total energy usage, while pellet production's energy demand varied from 7,39 Wh to 12,18 Wh based on fertiliser weight. ▪ Significant impacts were verified due to the MB harvesting (due to NaOH use), fertiliser production (urea), and soil application (nitrogen losses). Thus, considering NO_x emissions is essential. ▪ Alternative harvesting methods are recommended for reducing impacts. ▪ Overall, microalgae-based fertilisers showed lower environmental impacts than chemical fertilisers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ FU was limited by the study's timeframe, not covering the entire corn growth cycle, leading to a reliance on the dry matter of plant components. ▪ Natural coagulants are suggested for water treatment to reduce impacts, and further research is needed on harvesting techniques and their environmental effects. ▪ The advantages of biofertilisation from microalgae in wastewater are not fully captured in this LCA study. ▪ Improvements in the harvesting process are crucial, and future studies should consider ammonia volatilisation impacts and evaluate microalgae biofertilisers in various soil types.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The optimised scenario (C2-O) achieved a 52,56% reduction in total impacts compared to the conventional fertiliser (U). ▪ The uncertainty analysis showed that the U scenario had the least uncertainty, while scenarios using MB had higher variations in Water Consumption and Marine Eutrophication categories because of differences in avoided water during the cultivation process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The impacts of transportation were not included in this environmental study.
(Josa & Garfi, 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ System treating municipal wastewater (1). ▪ System treating food waste from plant-based products (2). ▪ System with microalgae cultivation in a standard growth medium (3). 	Agricultural Fields	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The standard growth medium scenario achieved the best social performance, particularly in health and safety, due to minimal contaminants and established regulations. ▪ The urban wastewater scenario posed higher risks, especially regarding worker safety and pathogen transmission from urban contaminants. ▪ The industrial wastewater scenario had more social impacts than standard growth medium but had lower impacts than urban wastewater, specifically considering worker health. ▪ Biogas and digestate from all scenarios had benefits by being substituted for fossil fuels. Nevertheless, the acceptance of bioproducts from wastewater is still challenging. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Results are based on modelled data. Therefore, further validation with operational data is needed. ▪ Social impacts are harder to quantify and depend on the social context of the data gathered. ▪ Research should explore methods to improve social acceptance of wastewater treatment, including eco-labelling. ▪ Future studies should integrate LCA with other sustainability tools for a more comprehensive overview.
(Suprihatin et al., 2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Chitosan production (1). ▪ Liquid fertiliser (2). ▪ Animal feed (3). 	-	<p><u>Chitosan production:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The main impacts observed in the global warming category were due to the decalcification and deproteinisation. ▪ For acidification and eutrophication categories, decalcification, washing, and deproteinisation are the process steps that contribute the most to the impacts. ▪ Regarding the cumulative energy demand, most of the impacts were connected to the decalcification, deproteinisation, and mixing processes. <p><u>Organic fertiliser production:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Global warming category: the main hotspots were decalcification, deproteinisation, quality control, and packaging. ▪ Acidification and eutrophication categories: Similar contributors as in chitosan production, along with mixing and stirring. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrating LCA with Economic and Social Life Cycle Analyses is needed. ▪ Process improvements for chitosan utilisation are crucial to enhance energy efficiency, reduce water use, and minimise waste.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cumulative energy demand: The main hotspots included decalcification, washing, and quality control. <p><u>Animal feed production:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global warming category: Most of the environmental impacts come from milling processes. Acidification, eutrophication, and cumulative energy demand categories: The main hotspots were related to animal feed processing activities. 	
(Mulya et al., 2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical fertiliser. Organic fertiliser. Microalgae fertiliser. 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The primary sources of electricity consumption in BBF production are the bioreactor processes (cultivation and fermentation), along with mixing, filling, and packaging. Transportation to foreign customers also had significant environmental impacts on emissions. Biofertilizer manufacturing emissions are 9,8 to 23,2 times lower than those of nitrogen-based chemical fertilisers like urea and ammonium nitrate. They have comparable emissions to potassium and phosphorus fertilisers. The energy-intensive Haber-Bosch process contributes the most to nitrogen fertiliser emissions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High energy-consuming fertilisers can have high emissions. Thus, using cleaner energy sources may help reduce these concerns. Mixing biofertilisers with other fertilisers may offset nitrogen fertiliser emissions. Future research should explore downstream emissions from biofertiliser applications for a more holistic LCA.
(Iglesias et al., 2025)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Northern spent mushroom substrate (SMS). Central SMS. Mediterranean SMS. 	Agricultural Fields	<p><u>Environmental results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The analysis of SMS fertilisers shows that the re-composting process accounts for over 90% of environmental impacts, mainly due to land use (60%) and fossil resource depletion (20%). Compared to a non-renewable benchmark, SMS performs better in climate change, ecotoxicity, and land use categories. However, the benchmark is more efficient in terms of water use. This study highlights the environmental advantages of SMS used as a soil improver compared to non-renewable alternatives. <p><u>Economic results:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The aggregated LCC results are 209,13 €/ton for the northern region, 164,67 €/ton for the central region, and -30,27 €/ton for the Mediterranean region. SMS fertilisers require more water but grant higher mushroom yields and revenues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The land use impact assessment does not consider changes in critical soil properties such as erosion resistance and biodiversity. Current tools for assessing use-phase emissions do not differentiate between molecular forms. The effectiveness of SMS as a soil improver compared to non-renewable options needs further investigation.

Reference	Scenarios/Processes considered	Application of BBFs	Main results	Limitations/Future research need
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Currently, SMS sales as a soil improver represent just 0,19% of the market. Nevertheless, increasing demand could become a significant revenue source for the mushroom industry. 	

The system design and integration are critical issues to consider when assessing the different systems' environmental performance. Overall, some studies showed that decentralised and integrated systems (*e.g.*, HRAP, hybrid decentralised treatment, and nutrient recovery) have better environmental performance than centralised or conventional approaches. This aligns well with the idea of producing fertilisers locally. Other studies that considered system expansion and avoided burdens (*e.g.*, energy or nutrient recovery, and nutrient substitution) demonstrated that the total environmental outcomes may be significantly improved. The assessed literature proved that bio-based fertilisers can offer strong potential for nutrient recycling, contributing to resource conservation and circular economy goals. However, factors like recovery efficiency and bioavailability vary significantly throughout BBF types and impact performance. Yet, several studies showed that bio-based fertilisers do not compromise crop yields or quality in most of the scenarios assessed, such as tomato, wheat, corn, and spinach trials. Other research works also support the conclusion that some BBFs may improve the soil quality, reduce nitrogen losses, and enhance plant resilience.

3.1.4. Environmental Concerns associated with BBF Production and Use

Regarding the environmental hotspots identified by the different authors, different conclusions may be taken. Firstly, electricity consumption (particularly when considering non-renewable sources) is one of the major contributors to the environmental impacts observed during BBF production (*e.g.*, mechanical dewatering in a filter press, drying, vacuum filtration, and biomass cultivation – microalgae harvesting). Thus, the energy source matters when producing bio-based fertilisers, and switching to more renewable energy sources (*e.g.*, photovoltaics) may significantly improve the environmental performance of BBFs. In addition, alternatives to energy-intensive processes are needed to reduce the environmental footprint of bio-based fertilisers (*e.g.* processes that include heat recovery). Secondly, the use of some consumables, namely during nutrient recovery processes (*e.g.*, sodium hydroxide, magnesium oxide), may significantly influence the environmental impacts. For example, regarding the struvite precipitation, trisodium phosphate and magnesium oxide were identified as hotspots by Ishii and Boyer, (2015). Thirdly, direct emissions (*e.g.* NH₃, N₂O, and NO_x) during the BBFs' life cycle also proved to be an issue of concern for the environment. Finally, other process steps like transport and storage may have a considerable influence on the environmental burdens.

From an economic point of view, BBF production demonstrates some potential to reduce costs when compared to synthetic fertiliser use, water treatment without valorisation of nutrient recovery, and energy generation without nutrient recovery. Nonetheless, BBF production often requires high direct investments and chemical inputs. Thus, it is possible to conclude that the financial feasibility of BBFs depends on technology choices, inputs costs, and treatment scale (*i.e.*, higher scales lead to a decrease in the total costs compared with lower ones, such as the lab scale).

Considering a socioeconomic perspective, some authors agreed that the public perception, regulation and market development are key for wider applications. However, despite the environmental benefits of BBFs obtained from wastes (*e.g.*, wastewater), they may raise some concerns about health, safety, and social acceptance.

The sensitivity of the results to key parameters and therefore the general uncertainty within the research works reviewed are considerably high. They show that results are sensitive to several

assumptions, such as nutrient (*e.g.*, nitrogen) content (when considering the nutrient-based fertiliser substitution), storage time, electricity consumption and source, and compost maturity. Moreover, the uncertainty analyses highlighted some variability across locations, technologies, and input parameters.

When looking for the limitations pointed out by the authors, it is worth summing up some of them. Many studies are limited to small scales (*i.e.*, lab) or modelled data, which may not reflect the processes when considering higher production scales, such as industrial. Thus, a lack of scalability and validation with operational or field data is often found. During the LCA studies, some key emissions (*e.g.* NH₃ or N₂O) are often not accounted for. This assumption may underestimate the environmental impacts associated with fertilisers' production. Moreover, impacts associated with the transport, downstream application, and microbial activity are frequently disregarded. Sometimes, the environmental assessments do not cover the entire life cycle of the BBFs or crop cycle, missing some potentially relevant steps like the use phase with potential long-term soil impacts. Other studies also highlighted that there is a need to integrate LCA approaches with economic and social assessments to have a more holistic overview of the impacts. Specifically, studies concluded that social and policy dimensions are almost underexplored, *e.g.*, social acceptance is rarely deeply studied, and there is a lack of policy-oriented research connecting BBF systems to pollution control incentives or eco-labelling. Other limitations are highlighted namely (1) potential agronomic benefits of BBFs are often unquantified (*e.g.*, effect on soil fertility, or water retention), (2) common data and methodological gaps such as lack of consistent, comparable data, outdated information and regionally narrow assumptions, and (3) the circularity potential of BBFs is not fully explored since many studies do not model the full supply chain, leaving the benefits of the circular economy underexplored. From an economic perspective, sometimes the economic assessment may be incomplete or oversimplified. In other words, cost analysis tends to exclude labour, maintenance and long-term economic impacts.

3.1.5. Assessment Benchmarks

Finally, some of the studies assessed and compared the environmental impacts of producing BBFs with conventional or standard fertilisers (benchmarks). Table 3.3 depicts these articles, identifying the type of BBFs studied and the selected benchmark against with the BBF is compared.

Table 3.3- Benchmarks considered by authors within the studied literature.

Source	Type of BBF	Benchmark
(Martínez-Blanco et al., 2009)	Compost	Mineral fertiliser (EcolInvent)
(Styles et al., 2018)	Liquid Digestate, and Digestate.	Conventional NPK fertiliser
(Arashiro et al., 2018)	Biofertiliser	Synthetic NPK fertiliser
(de Souza et al., 2019)	Biofertiliser	Urea (conventional mineral fertiliser)
(ten Hoeve et al., 2019)	Compost	Mineral P fertiliser
(J. de S. Castro et al., 2020)	Phosphate Biofertiliser (12% dry algae biomass with TSP).	TSP fertiliser
(Keng et al., 2020)	Compost	Chemical fertiliser
(González-Cencerrado et al., 2020)	Organic Fertiliser	Urea, Ammonium Sulphate (AS), Ammonium Nitrate (AN), and Diammonium Phosphate (DAP)
(Rupawalla et al., 2021)	Algae Fertiliser	Synthetic fertiliser (20.8% of total N).
(Yoshikawa et al., 2021)	Compost	Commercial Organic fertiliser – 8% N, 4% P ₂ O ₅ , and 4% K ₂ O.

(Pereira et al., 2023)	Organomineral Fertiliser (pelletised)	Granulated Urea
(Josa & Garfi, 2023)	Algae Fertiliser	Chemical fertiliser
(Mulya et al., 2024)	Biofertiliser (liquid)	Urea, AN, Ammonium Phosphate, Single Superphosphate, Triple Superphosphate, and Potassium Chloride.
(Iglesias et al., 2025)	Soil Improver	NPK fertiliser with carbon

It is important to note that most of the studies do not give a detailed description of the fertilisers used as benchmarks. Nevertheless, some conclusions may be drawn. Firstly, BBFs may have different characteristics and act as compost or even as soil improver. Secondly, BBF may replace different standard fertilisers, and the authors often consider a direct substitution of the fertiliser of 1:1 (in terms of total macronutrients). Finally, several conventional fertilisers were considered, with urea and NPK fertilisers being the most studied.

This deliverable will be mainly focus on the intermediary products. Therefore, the Hazard assessment was performed to the substances and materials that might be introduced into the production process of BBFs' ingredients. BBFs formulations are excluded from this, considering this will focus on occupational risks from processing ingredients - to be considered in D6.12 – “SSbD recommendations”.

3.2. Production Systems Under Study

3.2.1. Indo-3-acetic Acid (IAA)

IAA, the main naturally occurring auxin³, is essential for almost every aspect of plant growth and development (Zhao, 2012). In ReLEAF, IAA will be produced via solid state fermentation (SSF) of mixed food waste and agri-food residues, contributing to the circular bioeconomy and sustainable production of BBF ingredients.

SSF has emerged as an effective low-impact biotechnological process for IAA production. Several studies have described the production of IAA through SSF. Ghoreishi et al., (2024) demonstrated a bench-scale production process using *Trichoderma harzianum* CECT 2929 and grass clippings as the main substrate and pruning waste or wood chips as bulking agents. Several substances and materials were identified in the literature (Boondaeng et al., 2023; Ghoreishi et al., 2024; Saber et al., 2017) as relevant to be used during the production process of IAA, namely:

Microorganism/inoculum:

- *Trichoderma harzianum* as the inoculum for the solid-state fermentation process

Primary substrate and additives:

³ Auxin is a type of plant hormone that promotes the elongation of shoot cells in plants. It is produced at the head of stems and roots and travels to the zone of elongation (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/chemistry/auxin>).

- ScienceDirect® AI generated definition based on: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-91684-4.00028-1>

- Grass clippings a carbon-rich feedstock to be used as the primary source for fermentation
- Pruning waste/wood chips – bulking agent enhancing aeration and porosity.
- Tryptophan – metabolic precursor for microbial IAA biosynthesis

Inoculum Preparation Media Components:

- Malt, Exts., Malt extract agar, Potato dextrose agar for the inoculum preparation - nutrient media for fungal propagation
- Tween 80 Polysorbate - surfactant aiding in uniform spore dispersion

Medium Screening/Optimisation Phase:

- Peptone as organic nitrogen source promoting fungal biomass and used during the early medium screening phase
- Glucose as the primary carbon source which directly influences the microbial metabolism, biomass growth and secondary metabolism production

The identified substances and materials were qualitatively assessed for their intrinsic hazards, using the SSbD Framework – Step 1 (Hazard Assessment and Prioritisation). The classification was based on the REACH and CLP regulatory frameworks. In Table 3.4- List of assessed substances identified to produce IAA, grouped by the corresponding SSbD Criterion (H1, H2 and H3). and Table 3.5 are listed the identified substances and their corresponding group.

Table 3.4 - List of assessed substances identified to produce IAA, grouped by the corresponding SSbD Criterion (H1, H2 and H3).

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H1	
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H2	Tween 80 Polysorbate
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H3	Malt, Exts. Indole-3-acetic acid or indole acetic acid (IAA) Sodium phosphate

Table 3.5 - List of assessed substances identified for the production of IAA that have no classification or with lack of data for classification.

Substances with no classification or with lack of data for classification
Trichoderma harzianum
Malt extract agar
Potato dextrose agar
Tryptophan ((2S)-2-amino-3-(1H-indol-3-yl)propanoic acid)
Peptone
Glucose

IAA is listed in the Carcinogenic Potency Database (CPDB) (Gold et al., 1991, 2007; National Library of Medicine, 2025a), a single standardised and comprehensive repository of the results of 45 years of chronic, long-term carcinogenesis bioassays. Some agencies, including the U.S. EPA, FDA, and IARC, have referenced CPDB data when reviewing chemical risks. Data are included from 6153 experiments reported in the general literature and in the in Technical Reports of the National Cancer Institute/National Toxicology Program (NCI/NTP). Information is given in the CPDB on strain, sex, route of compound administration, target organ, histopathology, author's opinion about carcinogenicity, and reference to the published paper, as well as quantitative data on statistical significance, tumour incidence, dose-response curve shape, length of experiment, duration of dosing, and dose-rate (National Library of Medicine, 2025b). Although IAA is not conclusively classified as a carcinogen by agencies like IARC or ECHA, its presence in CPDB indicates historical toxicological interest.

The study of Ismail, (2022) reported some concerns regarding the use of IAA, especially at high concentrations, to the human health, animals and the environment. The exposure of rats to IAA produced anaemia, leukopenia, neutrophilia, lymphopenia, and a significant increase in activities of serum transaminase, gamma-glutamyl transferase, creatine kinase-myocardial band, creatine kinase-muscle type, and levels of serum creatinine, sodium, chloride, and potassium. Furthermore, serum levels of testosterone, gonadotropins, and leptin significantly declined. The changes in most of measured parameters continued after IAA withdrawal. Histopathological alterations in different tissues supported these changes. In conclusion, subacute exposure to IAA at a high concentration could exert hematotoxicity and toxic effects on many soft organs and its withdrawal led to incomplete recovery of animals. Thus, IAA should be used cautiously as extensive use of it at high concentrations can cause harmful effects on the environment, animals and human beings.

Figure 3.7 shows the hazard classification distribution of 10 substances involved in IAA production according to Step 1 of the SSbD framework. Step 1 focuses on intrinsic hazardous properties of chemicals and materials, evaluating human health hazards, environmental hazards, and physical hazards before assessing safety during production and use.

Figure 3.7 – Hazard classification of the substances and materials typically used during the production of IAA.

The results highlight potential barriers to SSbD compliance due to the fundamental rule in the framework., which is that substances and materials must meet minimum safety criteria to proceed as SSbD-compliant. The findings reveal that:

- 6 out of 10 substances (60%) remain unclassified, which indicate insufficient hazard data rather than proven safety.
- 4 substances (40%) show classified hazard levels (H2 and H3), with H2 representing higher concern levels.

Additionally, IAA is classified with hazard properties included in the H3 criterion.

IAA in EU regulation:

Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 governs the authorisation, marketing, and use of plant protection products within the EU. For an active substance such as IAA to be included in plant protection products, it must be approved following the criteria outlined in this regulation. However, IAA has not been approved as an active substance under this framework. Specifically, Commission Decision 2008/941/EC, issued on December 8, 2008, determined the non-inclusion of certain active substances, including IAA, in Annex I of Council Directive 91/414/EEC, leading to the prohibition of their use in plant protection products. Consequently, placing on the market or using plant protection products containing IAA is prohibited in the EU.

Additionally, IAA is subjected to PIC - Prior Informed Consent Regulation - Regulation (EU) No 649/2012. Indolylacetic Acid or Indole Acetic acid (CAS n.: 87-51-4) is banned from export from the EU to non-EU states, under PIC Regulation.

The PIC Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 649/2012) implements the Rotterdam Convention on the Prior Informed Consent Procedure for certain hazardous chemicals and pesticides in international trade. It regulates the import and export of specific hazardous chemicals and places obligations on companies wishing to export these chemicals to non-EU countries. Given that IAA is prohibited for use in plant protection products within the EU due to its non-approval under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009, its export for such purposes would also be subject to the provisions of the PIC Regulation. Exporters

would need to comply with notification requirements and obtain explicit consent from the importing country before proceeding.

PIC regulation text: “*It is prohibited to place on the market or use plant protection products containing indolylacetic acid because this active substance has not been approved under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market and repealing Council Directives 79/117/EEC and 91/414/EEC (OJ L 309, 24.11.2009, p. 1-50) pursuant to Commission Decision 2008/941/EC of 8 December 2008 concerning the non-inclusion of certain active substances in Annex I to Council Directive 91/414/EEC and the withdrawal of authorisations for plant protection products containing these substances (OJ L 335, 13.12.2008, p. 91-93)*”.

Indolylacetic acid has therefore been added to Part 1 and Part 2 of Annex I by Commission Regulation (EU) No 834/2011 of 19 August 2011 amending Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 689/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the export and import of dangerous chemicals (European Union, 2011).

Due to human and environmental impact uncertainties and the lack of comprehensive data, regulatory authorities have opted for a precautionary approach, leading to the non-approval of IAA in plant protection products within the EU.

***Trichoderma harzianum* in EU regulation:**

Trichoderma harzianum is currently under a pre-registration process for approval EU, Pesticides, Maximum Residue Levels: Annexes II, III, IV, VII, Regulation 396/2005/EC, last amended by Regulation (EU) 2024/1078, OJ L of 16 April 2024, for the strains T-22 and ITEM 908.

Regarding the Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 - Plant Protection Products, *Trichoderma harzianum* T-22 is currently approved for uses as fungicide for plant protection, until 15th April 2025, under the Regulation 1107/2009/EC. It is important to note that, several extensions for the approval of this substance have been published. In fact, on 21st January 2025 was published the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2025/99 document, extending for the approval period for the use of active substances, i.e., *Trichoderma harzianum*. The expiration of approval will be replaced by 30th November 2026 (European Union, 2025).

From EFSA - European Food Safety Authority, for the active substances *Trichoderma asperellum* (formerly *T. harzianum*) strains ICC012, T25 and TV1, *Trichoderma atroviride* (formerly *T. harzianum*) strain T11, *Trichoderma gamsii* (formerly *T. viride*) strain ICC080, *Trichoderma harzianum* strains T-22 and ITEM 908, the European Food Safety Authority (‘the Authority’) requested additional information in accordance with Article 13(3) of Implementing Regulation (EU) No 844/2012. It was submitted by the given deadline of 14 July 2022 and additional time will be needed for its evaluation and for the related conclusion by risk assessors as well as the ensuing risk management decision in accordance with Articles 13 and 14 of Implementing Regulation (EU) No 844/2012 (European Union, 2023).

Concerning the use of *Trichoderma harzianum*, as the inoculum for the solid-state fermentation (SSF) process, there are a variety of strains that, if handled in powder form, can pose different exposure hazards, depending on factors such as spore concentration, particle size, and presence of secondary

metabolites or contaminants. The main potential hazards include (EFSA, 2013; EPA, 2000; Martinez et al., 2023):

1. Respiratory Hazards resulting from inhalation exposure:

Fine powders containing fungal spores can become airborne and be inhaled and potentially cause respiratory irritation.

Some strains may have higher sporulation rates, which potential lead to increased inhalation risks.

Although *T. harzianum* is generally considered non-pathogenic, there are evidence that prolonged exposure to high concentrations of spores may induce allergic reactions or hypersensitivity pneumonitis in sensitive individuals.

Strains with known pulmonary toxicity concerns (e.g., EPA classified some *T. harzianum* strains as Toxicity Category II for pulmonary effects) could present a greater risk of lung irritation.

2. Dermal & Eye Irritation:

Powder formulations can cause skin irritation or sensitization, especially if the strain produces enzymes or metabolites with irritant properties.

The SSF-based production of IAA using organic residues offers a circular and bio-based alternative for the development of BBFs. However, a precautionary approach is warranted due to the limited toxicological data, especially concerning long-term exposure and environmental fate. The hazard assessment highlights the need for:

- Substitution or minimisation of substances under H2 or H3 categories, according with the principles of the SSbD framework.
- Controlled handling of biological agents (*Trichoderma harzianum*) and chemical precursors.
- Regulatory compliance with EU pesticide, chemical export, and occupational safety guidelines.

The consortium is currently taking these results into consideration, and an approach to address the safety requirements is under evaluation.

3.2.2. Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) is a group of biodegradable polymers synthesized by a variety of microorganisms under unbalanced growth conditions as intracellular storage compounds in discrete granular form in their cytoplasm (Alves et al., 2011).

From the environmental point of view, PHA is recognised for being biodegradable and eco-friendly. Although many efforts have been made for a sustainable production of this bio-polymer, there are currently some concerns regarding the downstream processes and high costs (Kogje et al., 2025). Some authors highlighted that energy (due to high energy-intensive approaches) and fermentation may be some of the potential hotspots of the PHA production, namely when considering pure-culture processes (Mineo et al., 2024; Morgan-sagastume et al., 2016). Recently, the research on PHA production from sewage sludge has gained credit due to the increasing need to implement circular economy strategies in the water sector (Mannina & Mineo, 2024; Mineo et al., 2024). Specifically,

Mineo et al., (2024) performed an LCA study to evaluate the environmental implications of PHA production from sewage sludge. To do so, two different pilot configurations were studied: (1) aerobic dynamic feeding, and (2) Aerobic/anoxic configuration. Using a functional unit of 1 kg of PHA produced, the authors concluded that configuration 2 is more environmentally friendly than configuration 1. For these two configurations, the main environmental hotspots are slightly different. Thus, for scenario 1, the selection of PHA producers (31%), PHA accumulation (27%), and acidogenic fermentation (20%) were the major contributors to the environmental burdens observed. On the other hand, Ammonia nitritation, PHA accumulation, and acidogenic fermentation were the main hotspots of scenario 2, accounting for 24%, 23%, and 18% of the impacts, respectively.

Morgan-sagastume et al., (2016) assessed the technical and environmental performance of integrating a mixed microbial culture (MMC) for PHA production (MMC-PHA) with a full-scale municipal wastewater treatment plant. For this study, four different process alternatives were studied and compared with a reference plant throughout the following functional unit: “the treatment of the same influent wastewater flow rate with treatment to comply with effluent water quality standards for all process configurations”. When compared with the reference scenario, the results demonstrated that the alternative scenarios (1) need lower electric energy, mostly because of the aeration needs, and (2) produce less biogas and sludge, which leads to lower emissions. Moreover, alternative PHA scenarios may reduce GWP, acidification, eutrophication and photo-oxidant formation potential by 40%, 70%, 90%, and 75%, respectively, when compared with the reference case. Specifically, freshwater and marine eutrophication potential were closely linked to the specifications of the effluent, *i.e.*, N and P discharges. Overall, the LCA results suggested that individual municipal wastewater treatment plants could become sources of valuable renewable raw materials beyond just biogas, energy, and heat.

Regarding safety requirements compliance, the production of PHAs was evaluated and the substances and materials identified as relevant and necessary for the production process were qualitatively assessed with the respect to their intrinsic hazard properties. From literature (Bengtsson et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2018; Morgan-Sagastume et al., 2015) and the questionnaires provided to the ReLEAF partners, around 45 substances were identified with potential to be used during the production process of PHA. In Table 3.6 are listed the identified substances per function and production process stage.

Table 3.6 – List of relevant substances that may be used during the production of PHAs.

Substance	Function	Stage
<i>Acetic acid</i>	SCFA ⁴ – product or added	Acidogenic Fermentation
<i>Butyric acid</i>	SCFA – product or added	
<i>Caproic acid</i>	SCFA – product or added	
<i>Propionic acid</i>	SCFA – product or added	
<i>Valeric acid</i>	SCFA – product or added	
<i>Hydrochloric acid</i>	pH control – acidification	

⁴ SCFAs: short-chain fatty acids

Substance	Function	Stage	
<i>Sulphuric acid</i>	pH control – acidification		
<i>Sodium bicarbonate</i>	pH buffering		
<i>Acetic, Butyric, Propionic, Valeric acids</i>	Feeding substrates (SCFAs)	Selection Reactor	
<i>Ammonium chloride</i>	Nitrogen source – growth phase		
<i>Thiourea</i>	Sulphur/nitrogen source		
<i>Magnesium sulphate (anhydrous/hydrated)</i>	Micronutrient – enzyme cofactor		
<i>Calcium chloride</i>	Micronutrient – cell wall stability		
<i>Iron(III) chloride (anhydrous/hydrated)</i>	Micronutrient – redox enzymes		
<i>Manganese chloride (anhydrous/hydrated)</i>	Micronutrient – antioxidant enzymes		
<i>Zinc sulphate (anhydrous/heptahydrate)</i>	Micronutrient		
<i>Cobalt dichloride (anhydrous/hydrated)</i>	Micronutrient – vitamin B12 synthesis		
<i>Copper sulphate (anhydrous/hydrated)</i>	Micronutrient – enzymatic activity		
<i>Boric acid</i>	Micronutrient – cell wall/membrane function		
<i>Disodium molybdate (anhydrous/hydrated)</i>	Micronutrient – nitrate reductase cofactor		
<i>Potassium iodide or Potassium iodite</i>	Micronutrient – oxidative stress mediator		
<i>Potassium dihydrogen phosphate</i>	Phosphate source and buffer		
<i>EDTA</i>	Chelating agent – improves metal bioavailability		
<i>Acetic, Propionic, Butyric, Valeric acids</i>	Carbon source for PHA accumulation		PHA Production Reactor
<i>Methanol / Ethanol</i>	Co-substrates – sometimes used (strain-dependent)		
<i>Sodium hydroxide</i>	pH control		
<i>Sulphuric / Hydrochloric acid</i>	pH control		
<i>Sodium bicarbonate</i>	Buffer		
<i>Potassium dihydrogen phosphate</i>	Buffer and phosphate source		
<i>Chloroform</i>	PHA extraction solvent		
<i>Methanol / Ethanol</i>	Washing solvents / PHA precipitation		
<i>Sodium hypochlorite</i>	Cell lysis agent (for biomass digestion)		
<i>Hydrogen peroxide</i>	Oxidative cell disruption or disinfection		
<i>Peracetic acid</i>	Sterilising / oxidative disruption agent		

The intrinsic hazard properties were identified, based on the information available in EU regulations, such as, REACH and CLP. In Table 3.7 and Table 3.8 the substances were grouped by the criteria established for the Step 1 of the SSbD framework.

Table 3.7 - List of assessed substances identified for the production of PHAs, grouped by the corresponding SSbD Criterion (H1, H2 and H3).

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H1	Boric Acid Chloroform Cobalt Dichloride (anhydrous) Cobalt Dichloride (hydrated) Copper Sulphate (anhydrous) Copper Sulphate (hydrated) Ethanol Potassium Iodite Potassium Iodide Sulphuric Acid
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H2	Ammonium Chloride EDTA Iron Trichloride (anhydrous and hydrated) Manganese Chloride (anhydrous and hydrated) Sodium Hypochlorite Thiourea Methanol
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H3	Acetic Acid Butyric Acid Calcium Chloride Caproic Acid Hydrochloric acid (hydrogen chloride) Hydrogen Peroxide Magnesium Sulphate (anhydrous) Magnesium Sulphate (hydrated) Paracetic acid Potassium dihydrogen phosphate Propionic Acid Sodium Bicarbonate Sodium Hydroxide Disodium molybdate (anhydrous) Disodium molybdate (hydrated) Potassium dihydrogen phosphate Propionic acid Sodium bicarbonate Sodium hydroxide Sodium hypochlorite Sodium molybdate (dihydrate) Disodium molybdate (anhydrous) Valeric Acid

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
	Zinc sulphate (heptahydrate) Zinc sulphate (anhydrous)

Table 3.8 - List of assessed substances identified for the production of PHAs that have no classification or with lack of data for classification.

Substances with no classification or with lack of data for classification
Poly(hydroxybutyrate) PHBV Powder

Figure 3.8 shows the hazard classification distribution of the 45 substances involved in IAA production according to Step 1 of the SSbD framework.

Figure 3.8 – Hazard classification of the substances and materials typically used during the production of PHAs

The findings from the qualitative assessment show the following:

- H1 Prevalence (22%): 10 substances in group H1 (e.g., chloroform, cobalt compounds) that align with EU-defined "substances of very high concern" (SVHCs), requiring substitution under SSbD principles.
- 9 substances in group H2 such as thiourea (toxic to aquatic life) and sodium hypochlorite (oxidizing) highlight the need for an intermediate assessment to balance functionality and safety.
- H3 Dominance (55%): 25 substances in group H3. This group of substances possesses manageable risks but underscores the importance of lifecycle exposure assessments in Step 2 and 3 of SSbD.

Overall, in alignment with SSbD principles and the implications of these results, the substances identified in H1 group must undergo iterative redesign to replace with safer alternatives and meet the hazard elimination goal, ensuring PHAs materials become SSbD-compliant.

Regulatory landscape in the EU: Microorganisms in PHAs Production

The production of PHAs through microbial fermentation involves the handling of biological agents in industrial, pilot-scale and laboratory settings, often under controlled (contained) conditions. These processes must be governed by a series of EU regulations and directives designed to ensure the safe use of microorganisms, protect human health (workers, consumers, and public health), and safeguard the environment. The use of microorganisms for PHAs production in the EU is comprehensively regulated under a several regulations, directives and guidelines, that integrates biosafety, worker protection, chemical management, and environmental considerations, whether using wild-type strains or engineered organisms.

The EU framework includes Directive 2009/41/EC, which sets out requirements for the contained use of genetically modified microorganisms (GMMs), based on a risk classification system and appropriate containment levels. All industrial and research activities involving GMMs must be notified or authorised by national competent authorities. In addition, Directive 2000/54/EC ensures the protection of workers exposed to biological agents, mandating risk assessments, implementation of control measures, and health surveillance where necessary, regardless of whether the microorganisms are genetically modified. Where fermentation substrates include organic waste or animal by-products, Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 governs their use to prevent risks to public and animal health.

3.2.3. Ammonium Salts

The recovery of ammonium salts from organic waste streams, particularly sewage sludge, has emerged as a key strategy in circular economy approaches within wastewater treatment.

Traditionally, nitrogen in wastewater is treated as a pollutant, but recent developments in nutrient recovery technologies have shifted this paradigm, enabling the valorisation of ammoniacal nitrogen as a valuable input for fertiliser production. One of the most advanced techniques is the use of membrane contactors (Reyes Alva et al., 2025; Richter et al., 2020), which selectively recover gaseous ammonia (NH₃) from sludge digestion liquors by shifting the pH and temperature conditions. The recovered ammonia is captured into acidic trapping solutions, most commonly sulphuric acid or citric acid, to produce ammonium sulphate or ammonium citrate, respectively. These recovered salts are directly applicable as fertiliser ingredients or can be further blended into bio-based fertiliser formulations.

Importantly, the production and application of Ammonium Salts recovered from sewage sludge must be accompanied by rigorous safety and risk assessments. Potential concerns include the presence of heavy metals, organic micropollutants, pathogens, and pharmaceutical residues that may be co-extracted during processing. These contaminants could pose risks to soil health, food safety, and human health if not adequately controlled. Therefore, compliance with existing regulations, such as the Fertilising Products Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, and alignment with Safe-by-Design principles are essential to ensure the safe use of these materials in agriculture. Several substances and materials were identified in the literature (Reyes Alva et al., 2025; Richter et al., 2020) as relevant to be used during the recovery process of ammonium salts, namely:

Table 3.9 – List of relevant substances that may be used during the production of Ammonium Salts

Substance	Function	Stage
<i>Sodium hydroxide</i>	To increase pH of feed water to promote NH ₃ formation	Basification of supernatant
<i>Sulphuric Acid</i>	Trapping solution to recover ammonia as ammonium sulphate	Extraction solution pH = 1
<i>Citric Acid (alternative)</i>	Alternative trapping solution to produce ammonium citrate	
<i>Ammonium Sulphate</i>	Recovered ammonium	Membrane stripping – Recovery of ammonium

The intrinsic hazard properties were identified, based on the information available in EU regulations, such as, REACH and CLP. In Table 3.10 the substances were grouped by the criteria established for the Step 1 of the SSbD framework.

Table 3.10 - List of assessed substances identified for the production of ammonium salts, grouped by the corresponding SSbD criterion (H1, H2 and H3).

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H1	Sulphuric acid
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H2	_____
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H3	Sodium hydroxide Citric Acid Ammonium Sulphate

Figure 3.9 shows the hazard classification distribution of the 4 substances that can be involved in the recovery of ammonium salts by membrane stripping according to Step 1 of the SSbD framework.

Figure 3.9 - Hazard classification of the substances and materials typically used during the production of ammonium salts.

Ammonium salts recovery from sewage sludge using membrane contactors, can use both sulphuric acid and citric acid as trapping solutions to convert recovered gaseous ammonia into fertilisable salts, namely ammonium sulphate and ammonium citrate. While sulphuric acid remains the conventional choice due to its strong acidity and widespread use in fertiliser manufacturing, citric acid might be used as a safer and more environmentally sustainable alternative. Citric acid is a naturally occurring, biodegradable organic acid with low toxicity and corrosivity, reducing risks to operators and infrastructure. Importantly, the resulting ammonium citrate not only supplies nitrogen but also contributes chelating properties, enhancing micronutrient availability in soils. Studies such as those by Richter et al., (2020) and Reyes Alva et al., (2025) Reyes Alva et al. (2025) have demonstrated the technical feasibility and agronomic potential of citric acid-based recovery. As such, for applications

aligned with sustainable agriculture and circular economy goals, citric acid offers a compelling option for safer nutrient recycling from organic waste.

Overall, in alignment with SSbD principles and the implications of these results, sulphuric acid which was identified in H1 group must undergo iterative redesign to replace with safer alternatives and meet the hazard elimination goal, ensuring the recovery of ammonium salts become SSbD-compliant.

3.2.4. Microbial Biomass, Collagen and Chitosan

Production of Dried Microbial Biomass from Fishing Industry Waste for BBFs

The transformation of fish and shellfish waste into dried microbial biomass for BBF applications follows a carefully structured process that enables nutrient recovery and waste valorisation, contributing to sustainable agricultural practices. The process begins with fishing industry by-products, including heads, viscera, bones, and trimmings, undergoing size reduction to facilitate microbial fermentation. Demineralisation using acidic treatments enhances the solubilisation of calcium compounds, improving nutrient accessibility. Additionally, enzymatic hydrolysis incorporating proteases and alcalase accelerates the degradation of organic matter, facilitating microbial assimilation and ensuring optimal conditions for subsequent microbial activity. Selected microorganisms are then introduced into the hydrolysed fish waste, initiating fermentation within a nutrient-enriched medium designed to support microbial proliferation. These microbial consortia drive bioconversion, yielding essential amino acids, proteins, and biostimulants that contribute to soil health and plant development. As microbial growth progresses, centrifugation and filtration steps are performed to separate microbial biomass from residual substrates, ensuring the purification and removal of excess non-utilised compounds. This stabilisation process helps maintain the integrity of the microbial biomass, optimising its bioavailability for agricultural applications. Finally, the purified microbial biomass undergoes vacuum drying or spray-drying, preserving biological activity and nutritional integrity. The resulting BBF is rich in proteins, amino acids, and bioactive compounds, enhancing soil fertility and plant growth while reinforcing circular economy principles and contributing to advancements in agricultural biotechnology and ecological innovation.

A qualitative assessment of the intrinsic hazards of the most frequently used and cited chemical substances, as identified in the consulted literature (Abdul Khalil et al., 2014; Ayodele et al., 2024; Ben Rebah & Miled, 2013; Javed et al., 2025; Kiruba N & Saeid, 2022; Maquen-Perleche et al., 2023; Vázquez et al., 2020; Wani et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2023b) was conducted and is presented below.

Table 3.11 – List of relevant substances that may be used during the productions of dried microbial biomass

Substance	Function	Stage
<i>Molasses</i>	Stimulates bacterial growth	Microbial Growth Stage (Fermenter)
<i>Yeast extract powder</i>	Nutrient source for microbial growth.	
<i>Peptone</i>	Provides peptides and amino acids for microbial growth	

Substance	Function	Stage
<i>Lysogeny broth (LB)</i>	Nutrient-rich medium for bacterial growth	
<i>Cleaning agent (unspecified)</i>	Maintains sterile conditions and prevents contamination	
<i>Glucose</i>	Carbon and energy source for microbial growth	
<i>Sodium hydroxide</i>	Protein hydrolysis and microbial activation agent.	Processing/Pre-Treatment Stage
<i>hydrochloric acid</i>	Adjusts pH, facilitates acid hydrolysis, and enhances nutrient release from microbial biomass	
<i>Sucrose</i>	Stabilises cells	Lyophilization Stage
<i>Skim milk</i>	Protects and stabilizes cells	

Table 3.12 - List of assessed substances for the production of dried microbial biomass, grouped by the corresponding SSbD criterion (H1, H2 and H3).

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H1. (SVHC)	Skim Milk*
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H2 (most harmful substances)	Glucose* Sucrose*
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H3.	Yeast extract powder Sodium hydroxide Hydrochloric Acid

(*) The categorisation was based on hazard statement codes from non-harmonised classifications reported in the ECHA registration dossiers, reflecting additional hazards not yet included in the official CLP classification for the substance concerned

Table 3.13 - List of assessed substances identified for the production of dried microbial biomass that have no classification or with lack of data for classification.

Substances with no classification or with lack of data for classification
Peptone (Lysogeny broth (LB)) Molasses

Figure 3.10 - Hazard classification of the substances that may be used during the productions of dried microbial biomass

Additional details regarding the qualitative assessment can be found in the Appendix.

According to the scientific literature, microorganisms such as *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Streptomyces spp.*, *Penicillium spp.*, and *Rhizopus oryzae* are commonly used as seed cultures during the microbial growth stage (fermentation) in the production of dried microbial biomass.

In accordance with current European Union legislation—specifically Directive 2000/54/EC on the protection of workers from risks related to exposure to biological agents at work—none of these microorganisms are classified within hazard groups that require specific containment measures (i.e., risk groups 2, 3, or 4).

Nevertheless, as these are viable microorganisms, their handling must comply strictly with Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP). This includes the application of appropriate hygiene protocols, containment measures, and waste management procedures to ensure operator safety and to prevent cross-contamination.

Recovery of Collagen from Fish Processing Waste and Wastewater for BBF Production

Collagen, a structural protein abundantly found in fish by-products such as scales, skin, and bones, offers valuable potential for bio-based fertilisers. Due to its high nitrogen content, extensive amino acid profile, and role in stimulating microbial activity, collagen can enhance soil fertility while supporting sustainable agriculture. The utilisation of collagen-based fertilisers aligns with circular economy principles, promoting waste valorisation and reducing dependence on synthetic fertilisers.

The extraction of collagen for BBFs follows a structured process involving physical, chemical, and enzymatic treatments. Initially, fish scales or skin undergo pre-treatment and demineralisation, where washing removes organic impurities. The scales are then treated with Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) or Hydrochloric acid (HCl) to eliminate calcium phosphate and hydroxyapatite, improving collagen solubility. The next step involves the removal of fat and non-collagenous proteins using Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) or Calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂), ensuring higher purity (Chinh et al., 2019; Chinh & Hoang, 2024; Jafari et al., 2020).

Following pre-treatment, extraction methods are employed to isolate collagen. Acid extraction utilises Acetic acid (CH₃COOH) to solubilise collagen fibres, yielding an acid-soluble fraction. Enzyme-assisted extraction applies Pepsin enzyme, which hydrolyses collagen cross-links, improving yield and purity. Additionally, Deep Eutectic Solvent (DES) extraction, using Choline chloride and Oxalic acid, offers a sustainable and eco-friendly approach to collagen isolation.

Purification and processing ensure the extracted collagen is suitable for fertiliser applications. Filtration and centrifugation remove residual impurities, and freeze-drying converts collagen into powder or liquid hydrolysate, optimising its bioavailability. The final collagen hydrolysate is rich in organic nitrogen, amino acids, and bioactive compounds, making it highly effective as a soil amendment.

Collagen-based fertilisers offer several agronomic benefits, including improved soil structure and enhanced water retention, increased microbial activity that promotes nutrient mineralisation, and enhanced plant nutrient uptake, particularly for nitrogen and phosphorus. The integration of collagen hydrolysate into fertiliser formulations reduces reliance on synthetic fertilisers, contributing to sustainable and regenerative agricultural practices.

The three articles examined in this study provide distinct insights into collagen extraction and applications. The first article explores various extraction techniques, particularly comparing acid based and DES methods, and focuses on yield optimisation. The second article analyses collagen's molecular structure and composition, detailing biomedical applications rather than its agricultural potential. The third article presents experimental optimisation techniques, including temperature, acid concentration, and extraction duration, which are crucial for large-scale production.

Overall, collagen extraction for bio-based fertilisers represents an innovative approach to resource efficiency in agriculture. The adoption of enzyme-assisted and DES-based methods ensures eco-friendly processing while maintaining the integrity of bioactive compounds in the final fertiliser product. By leveraging collagen hydrolysate, agricultural systems can achieve enhanced soil health,

plant productivity, and circular waste management (Chinh et al., 2019; Chinh & Hoang, 2024; Jafari et al., 2020).

A qualitative assessment of the intrinsic hazards of the most frequently used and cited chemical substances, as identified in the consulted literature (Chinh et al., 2019; Chinh & Hoang, 2024; Jafari et al., 2020), was conducted and is presented below.

Table 3.14 – LIST OF RELEVANT SUBSTANCES IDENTIFIED AS POTENTIALLY APPLICABLE IN THE EXTRACTION AND PRODUCTION OF COLLAGEN FROM FISH BY-PRODUCTS, INCLUDING FISH PROCESSING WASTE AND WASTEWATER.

Substance	Function	Stage
<i>Sodium Hydroxide</i>	Alkaline removal of fats and non-collagenous proteins	Pre-treatment or deproteinisation Stage
<i>Calcium Hydroxide</i>	Mild alkaline agent for impurity removal	
<i>Butan-1-ol</i>	Removes fats, lipids, and non-collagen proteins, preparing raw material for demineralisation and collagen extraction	
<i>Diethyl Ether</i>	Remove lipids and non-collagenous	
<i>Hydrochloric Acid</i>	Removes minerals such as calcium phosphates	Demineralisation Stage
<i>Ethylenediaminetetra acetic Acid (EDTA)</i>	Chelates calcium ions to remove minerals	
<i>Phosphoric Acid</i>	Removes mineral components by dissolving calcium salts	
<i>Sulphuric Acid</i>	Removes mineral components by dissolving calcium salts	
<i>Acetic Acid</i>	Solubilises collagen and adjusts pH	Collagen extraction stage
<i>Pepsin A</i>	Enzyme that breaks down non-collagen proteins	
<i>Citric Acid</i>	Mild acid used to solubilise collagen and adjust pH	
<i>Lactic Acid</i>	Mild organic acid used to solubilise collagen and adjust pH	
<i>Collagen</i>	Used as a binding matrix and in controlled-release mechanisms for both solid and liquid fertiliser ingredients (final product	Final product (after extraction and purification)

Table 3.15 - List of assessed substances identified in the extraction and production of collagen from fish by-products, including fish processing waste and wastewater, grouped by the corresponding SSbD criterion (H1, H2 and H3).

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H1. (SVHC)	Pepsin A Sulphuric Acid
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H2 (most harmful substances)	EDTA*
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H3.	Sodium hydroxide Calcium Hydroxide Hydrochloric Acid Acetic Acid Citric acid Lactic Acid Phosphoric acid Butan-1-ol Diethyl Ether

Table 3.16 - List of assessed substances identified for the production of collagen that have no classification or with lack of data for classification.

Substances with no classification or with lack of data for classification	Total number of substances
Collagen	1

Figure 3.11 - Hazard classification of the substances that may be used in the extraction and production of collagen from fish by-products, including fish processing waste and wastewater

Additional details regarding the qualitative assessment can be found in the Annex section.

Collagen, commonly sourced from animal by-products, is increasingly considered a functional additive in BBFs due to its biodegradability and potential to enhance soil structure and nutrient availability. Scientific evaluations by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) have determined that collagen hydrolysate is safe for human exposure under intended uses, primarily based on its assessment as a dietary supplement (EFSA Panel on Dietetic Products Nutrition and Allergies (NDA), 2011). Additionally, the EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards (BIOHAZ) concluded that collagen and gelatine derived from ruminant bones, when processed following stringent European Union safety standards, pose a negligible risk of Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE) transmission (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards (BIOHAZ), 2024). Moreover, collagen is not classified as a hazardous substance under the EU REACH regulation, supporting its safe use in agricultural applications, including BBFs.

These regulatory and scientific assessments collectively support that collagen can be safely incorporated into biobased fertilizers (BBFs), provided it is sourced and processed in compliance with applicable European safety standards. Under these conditions, no adverse effects on human health or the environment are currently identified.

Collagen is usually extracted from bovine and porcine skins, which raises concerns about disease transmission and religious limitations. Fish skins, a by-product of the fishing industry that contributes significantly to marine waste, offer a sustainable and safer alternative (Batista et al., 2025). From the environmental perspective, Batista et al., (2025) assessed and compared two different collagen extraction methods from fish skin wastes: (1) traditional alkaline-acid procedure, and (2) new process considering the use of natural deep eutectic solvents. The methods were simulated using SuperPro Design Software, and the LCA was performed considering a FU of 1 kg of pure collagen and a “cradle-to-gate” approach. The midpoint categories analysis demonstrated that method 2 outperforms scenario 1 in only 9 of 16 impact categories analysed. Thus, the potential advantages of the innovative process are not very clear. Nevertheless, the new collagen extraction process proved to have less 13% of the total environmental impacts than the traditional method. Moreover, the single-score analysis

showed that process 2 may be more environmentally friendly than the conventional scenario. Looking further for the results, the extraction and purification processes were the main environmental hotspots of the traditional extraction process. These steps contribute to 43% and 45% of the impacts, respectively, due to the consumption of acetic acid, deionised water and electricity. On the other hand, the consumables used (*i.e.*, citric acid and xylitol) make the extraction process the main hotspot of scenario 2, accounting for more than 90% of the total impacts. However, the authors highlighted that the uncertainty analysis results advise that conclusions about impact reduction should be made cautiously due to input variability.

Valorisation of Chitosan from Fish Industry Waste for BBF Applications

Chitosan, a biopolymer derived from chitin, is increasingly recognised for its biostimulant properties, making it a valuable component in bio-based fertiliser formulations. Extracted from fishing industry waste, including crustacean shells and fish by-products, chitosan enhances soil microbial interactions, nutrient retention, and plant defence mechanisms, supporting sustainable agriculture while promoting waste valorisation.

According to the literature (Chinh et al., 2019; Iñiguez-Moreno et al., 2024; Rocha-Pimienta et al., 2023), the extraction of chitosan follows a structured process involving chemical and enzymatic treatments to isolate chitin while preserving its functional integrity for agricultural applications. Initially, crustacean shells such as prawn, crab, or shrimp exoskeletons undergo mechanical cleaning and fine grinding to optimise extraction efficiency. The demineralisation process is conducted using Hydrochloric acid (HCl) at concentrations of 2–5%, dissolving calcium carbonate and improving chitosan yield and purity. Following demineralisation, the shell fragments are subjected to Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) at 5% and maintained at 70°C to remove residual proteins and lipids, ensuring chitin isolation. The purified chitin then undergoes deacetylation, where it is treated with high-concentration NaOH (40–50%) at 80°C. This step removes acetyl groups, increasing solubility and bioactivity, optimising chitosan's effectiveness for agricultural applications. The final purification stage involves filtration and centrifugation to eliminate residual contaminants, followed by vacuum drying to obtain high-purity chitosan suitable for BBF formulations.

The resulting chitosan hydrolysate plays a significant role in soil enhancement and microbial activity stimulation. Its primary benefits include improved nutrient retention, particularly nitrogen and phosphorus availability, enhanced plant defence mechanisms reducing pathogen susceptibility, increased microbial activity supporting organic matter decomposition and mineralisation, and an eco-friendly alternative to synthetic fertilisers, promoting sustainable agricultural practices. The three articles reviewed provide distinct perspectives on chitosan extraction and applications. The first article focuses primarily on chitosan extraction techniques, comparing acid-based and alkaline methods with an emphasis on yield optimisation and deacetylation degree. The second article examines physicochemical properties and molecular composition, detailing biopolymer structure rather than its direct application in agriculture. The third article evaluates biopolymer applications, mainly in antimicrobial functions for food packaging, with limited discussion on chitosan's potential as a soil amendment.

The extraction of chitosan from fishing industry waste presents a sustainable solution for bio-based fertilisers, improving agricultural productivity and advancing waste valorisation. The use of chemical deacetylation ensures high-purity chitosan, supporting soil fertility, plant growth, and circular economy principles.

A qualitative assessment of the intrinsic hazards of the most frequently used and cited chemical substances, as identified in the consulted literature (Chinh et al., 2019; Iñiguez-Moreno et al., 2024; Rocha-Pimienta et al., 2023), was conducted and is presented below.

Table 3.17 – List of relevant substances identified as potentially applicable in the extraction and production of chitosan from fish industry waste

Substance	Function	Stage
<i>Sodium Hydroxide</i>	Breaks down and removes proteins from the shells.	Deproteinisation Stage (Chemical method)
<i>Calcium Hydroxide</i>	Mild alkaline agent for removing proteins and impurities	
<i>Potassium Hydroxide</i>	Strong alkali used for deproteinisation by breaking down proteins and facilitating their removal	
<i>Calcium Bisulfite</i>	Used as a reducing agent to break down proteins and aid in their removal during deproteinisation	
<i>Potassium Carbonate</i>	Acts as a mild alkaline agent to assist in protein removal during deproteinisation	
<i>Sodium Carbonate</i>	Mild alkaline agent used to remove proteins during deproteinisation	
<i>Sodium Hydrogen Carbonate</i>	Mild alkaline agent used for deproteinisation by removing proteins and impurities	
<i>Disodium Sulfite</i>	Reducing agent that breaks disulfide bonds in proteins, facilitating deproteinisation	
<i>Sodium Hydrogensulfite</i>	Acts as a reducing agent to break disulfide bonds in proteins, aiding deproteinisation	
<i>Trisodium Phosphate</i>	Used as an alkaline agent to solubilize and remove proteins during deproteinisation	
<i>Disodium Sulfide</i>	Breaks down and removes proteins by cleaving disulfide bonds during deproteinisation (also applicable in microbiological extraction methods)	
<i>Lactic acid</i>	Breaks down proteins, aiding in the removal of non-chitinous proteins from the raw material	
<i>Magnesium sulfate</i>	Acts as a processing aid to enhance the efficiency of protein removal	
<i>Potassium Phosphate, Dibasic</i>	Acts as a buffering agent to maintain pH stability during extraction processes (also applicable in microbiological extraction methods).	

Substance	Function	Stage
<i>Hydrochloric Acid 37%</i>	Removes minerals (mainly calcium carbonate) from crustacean shells	Demineralisation Stage (Chemical methos)
<i>Nitric Acid</i>	Removes minerals (e.g., calcium carbonate) from crustacean shells by acid dissolution	
<i>Sulphuric Acid</i>	Dissolves calcium salts to remove mineral components from shells	
<i>Acetic acid</i>	Mild organic acid used to dissolve calcium carbonate and remove minerals from shells	
<i>Formic Acid</i>	Removes minerals by dissolving calcium carbonate	
<i>Calcium hydroxide</i>	Assists in mineral removal by precipitating calcium salts	
<i>Lactic acid</i>	Acidifies the environment to dissolve inorganic minerals such as calcium carbonate, removing mineral content.	
<i>Acetone</i>	Removes pigments and other colouring impurities	Decolourisation Stage
<i>Hydrogen peroxide</i>	Used in the decolorization process to remove pigments and bleach the chitin; considered an optional step	
<i>Potassium Permanganate</i>	Used in the decolorization process to remove pigments from chitin (optional step)	
<i>Sodium Hypochlorite</i>	Used in the decolorization process to remove pigments from chitin (optional step)	
<i>Sodium Hydroxide</i>	Removes acetyl groups ($-COCH_3$) from chitin to convert it into chitosan .	Deacetylation Stage (Chemical method)
<i>Chitosan</i>	Biodegradable additive improving nutrient use, plant defense, and soil health in BBFs.	Final product
<i>Glucose</i>	Acts as a carbon source and energy substrate, facilitating microbial fermentation processes during biological and emerging chitosan extraction technologies.	biological and emerging technology

Table 3.18 - list of assessed substances identified in the extraction and production of chitosan from fish industry waste (fish and shellfish), grouped by the corresponding SSbD criterion (H1, H2 and H3).

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H1. (SVHC)	Sulphuric Acid
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H2 (most harmful substances)	Disodium Sulphide* Acetone* Hydrogen peroxide* Potassium permanganate Sodium hypochlorite Glucose*
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H3.	Hydrochloric Acid Sodium Hydroxide Nitric Acid Acetic Acid Formic Acid Calcium Hydroxide Potassium Hydroxide Potassium Carbonate Sodium Carbonate Sodium Hydrogen Carbonate Disodium Sulfite Sodium Hydrogensulfite Trisodium Phosphate Lactic Acid Magnesium Sulfate Potassium Phosphate, Dibasic Chitosan

Table 3.19 - List of assessed substances identified for the production of chitosan from fish industry waste (fish and shellfish), that have no classification or with lack of data for classification.

Substances with no classification or with lack of data for classification
Calcium Bisulphite

Figure 3.12 - Hazard classification of the substances that may be used in the extraction and production of chitosan from fish industry waste

Additional details regarding the qualitative assessment can be found in the table included in the Annex section.

After initial screening, hazard identification, and categorisation, the following steps can support the SSbD alignment in collagen, chitosan, and microbial biomass production:

- H1 Group Substances: Prioritise iterative redesign to eliminate hazards entirely by replacing them with safer alternatives.
- H2/H3 Group Substances: Replace or minimise usage while maintaining functional performance.

This phased approach ensures collagen, chitosan and dried microbial biomass meet SSbD requirements by systematically addressing risks across all hazard tiers.

Following the initial screening, hazard identification, and grouping according to the defined criteria, the cut-off criterion must be implemented. In alignment with SSbD principles and the implications of the results obtained from the assessment performed to the production of collagen, chitosan and microbial biomass, the substances identified in H1 group must undergo iterative redesign to replace with safer alternatives and meet the hazard elimination goal, while the substances grouped in H2 and H3, must be replaced or minimized, ensuring PHAs materials become SSbD-compliant.

Chitosan is increasingly recognised for its multifunctional applications in agriculture. It enhances nutrient uptake, promotes plant resistance to pathogens, and improves soil structure, making it a valuable additive in BBFs.

Regulatorily, chitosan is approved as a basic substance for plant protection under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009, confirmed by Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/456 (European Union, 2022), supporting its safe, natural use in agriculture. It is also listed as a novel food under Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/2470 (European Union, 2017), indicating an established safety profile.

ECHA does not classify chitosan as hazardous to human health or the environment. Furthermore, the EFSA Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues (PPR) found no toxicological concerns and concluded environmental exposure after typical use, including in fertilisers, is below natural background levels, minimizing ecological risks (EFSA Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues (PPR), 2025).

When used in compliance with relevant EU legislation—including Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 and Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/456—and following established good manufacturing practices (GMP) for agricultural inputs, chitosan can be safely incorporated into biobased fertilizers (BBFs) without posing risks to human health or the environment. However, improper production, handling, or application outside of these regulatory and quality frameworks could potentially lead to safety concerns.

The microorganisms involved in the biological chitosan extraction process from fish industry waste—such as *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactococcus lactis*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Bacillus* spp., *Serratia marcescens*, and others—are widely recognised as safe for applications in food and feed, based on their inclusion in the Qualified Presumption of Safety (QPS) list by EFSA and their recognition as "Generally Recognised As Safe" (GRAS) by the FDA, as reported in recent studies (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards (BIOHAZ), 2025; Iñiguez-Moreno et al., 2024).

Regarding worker protection, these microorganisms are not classified within risk groups that would require specific containment measures under Directive 2000/54/EC (European Union, 2000) on the protection of workers from risks related to exposure to biological agents at work. None of the microorganisms mentioned fall within risk groups 2, 3, or 4, which would necessitate additional safety measures. However, it is recommended to follow standard biosafety protocols when handling any biological agents. These protocols typically include using appropriate Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), such as gloves, lab coats, and face protection, as well as ensuring proper ventilation in working areas. Special care should be taken when handling *Bacillus* spp. and *Serratia marcescens*, as these organisms are opportunistic pathogens that may pose a risk of infection to immunocompromised individuals (EU OSHA, 2023).

Regarding the use of these microorganisms in bio-based products or biocides, it is important to note that compliance with Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 (European Union, 2019) on fertilising products or Regulation (EC) No 528/2012 (European Union, 2012b) on biocidal products is not inherently ensured. Compliance is contingent upon the specific authorisation of each microorganism strain and its intended application, which requires thorough safety and efficacy evaluations. Consequently, it cannot be stated that these microorganisms are universally authorised for such uses without undergoing the necessary regulatory assessment.

Chitosan may be applied in different sectors, namely the cosmetic industry, packaging and food industry, medicine, textile industry and agriculture (Batista et al., 2025). Muñoz et al., (2018) evaluate the life-cycle environmental impacts of producing chitosan in Europe and India with two different purposes and considerations. Scenario 1 includes the local production of chitosan in India, with its general application, namely in agriculture, using shrimp shells. On the other hand, scenario 2 assumes a globalised production of chitosan in Europe to be used in the medical sector and considering snow crab shells as raw material. The LCA study assumed a FU of 1 kg of chitosan and a "cradle-to-gate"

approach. The environmental impact assessment showed that the chemicals used, *i.e.*, hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide, and ammonia emissions when protein sludge is employed as a fertiliser, were the main hotspots of scenario 1 (Indian production). Regarding the European production, the results depicted that energy consumption, namely heat obtained from coal and electricity, was the main contributor to the impacts observed. Comparatively, the Indian scenario has lower environmental impacts than the European one in 4 of 5 impact categories assessed, *i.e.*, climate change, freshwater ecotoxicity, land use and water use. The exception was the acidification category. For this midpoint, the European production scenario had lower impacts due to the use of crab shells that are not forward to composting. According to the authors, this process is highly connected with ammonia emissions and, consequently, the acidification potential. Overall, the two scenarios have different environmental performance mainly because of different processes' assumptions, including: (1) raw materials used (crab shells vs. shrimp shells), (2) location (produced in local vs. global production), and (3) application field (general application vs. medical sector).

3.2.5. Struvite

Struvite precipitation is one of the process routes used to recover P and N nutrients from wastewater. To do so, the available literature shows that currently, two different waste streams may be used, *i.e.*, wastewater from a wastewater treatment plant or a split urine flow (Sena & Hicks, 2018). Concerning the former, Ravi et al., (2022) performed LCA studies with two different main objectives. On the one hand, aim 1 was to assess and compare the environmental performance of a wastewater treatment plant before and after the implementation of struvite recovery. On the other hand, aim 2 was to explore other scenarios assuming the struvite recovery but comparing the impacts of different wastewater sludges' end-of-life scenarios, namely sludge valorisation in cement kilns, mono-incineration, co-incineration with municipal solid waste, and land application. To get the answers to these objectives, two FUs were considered, namely (1) "1 kg of plant-available P recovered in the form of struvite, and treatment of its equivalent wastewater inflow, *i.e.* 3927 m³", and (2) 1 ton of sludge (digested). The results of the environmental impact assessment showed that recovering struvite enhanced the environmental performance of the wastewater treatment plant. Regarding the second objective, the scenario with mono-incineration had worse environmental performance than the current scenario (except for the fossil fuel depletion category), which considers 1/3 of the sludges' valorisation in cement kilns and 2/3 of co-incineration.

Importantly, the production and application of struvite recovered from sewage sludge must be accompanied by rigorous safety and risk assessments. Potential concerns include the presence of heavy metals, organic micropollutants, pathogens, and pharmaceutical residues that may be co-extracted during processing. These contaminants could pose risks to soil health, food safety, and human health if not adequately controlled. Therefore, compliance with existing regulations, such as the Fertilising Products Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, and alignment with Safe-by-Design principles are essential to ensure the safe use of these materials in agriculture. Several substances and materials were identified in the literature (Cañas et al., 2023; Reyes Alva et al., 2025; Richter et al., 2020; Saerens et al., 2021) as relevant to be used during the production process of struvite and are listed in Table 3.20.

Table 3.20 - List of relevant substances that may be used during the production of Struvite.

Substance	Function	Stage
<i>Sodium hydroxide</i>	To increase pH of feed water to promote NH ₃ formation	Struvite production with the supernatant
<i>Magnesium Chloride</i>	Source of Mg ²⁺ for struvite precipitation	
<i>Hydroxylapatite</i>	Competing phosphate precipitate, sometimes forms alongside struvite depending on calcium levels	
<i>Ammonium chloride</i>	To adjust NH ₄ ⁺ levels	
<i>Sodium bicarbonate</i>	Buffering agent, may help control pH	
<i>Struvite (Magnesium ammonium phosphate hexahydrate)</i>	Product	
<i>Hydroxylapatite</i>	May be used as sorbent/polishing agent	Struvite cleaning with water
<i>Citric Acid</i>	Mild organic acid for cleaning struvite; can also be used to extract phosphorus from solids	
<i>Nitric acid</i>	Strong acid, can be used to remove impurities or in phosphorus leaching	
<i>Hydrochloric acid</i>	Common cleaning agent; can also be used in Phosphorus leaching steps from sludge solids	
<i>Potassium chloride</i>	Used in sequential extraction procedures to remove soluble fractions; can be part of washing protocols between extraction steps	
<i>Struvite (Magnesium ammonium phosphate hexahydrate)</i>	End product	

The intrinsic hazard properties were identified, based on the information available in EU regulations, such as, REACH and CLP. In Table 3.21Table 3.7 the substances were grouped by the criteria established for the Step 1 of the SSbD framework.

Table 3.21 - List of assessed substances identified for the production of struvite, grouped by the corresponding SSbD criterion (H1, H2 and H3).

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H1	_____
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H2	_____
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H3	Sodium hydroxide Magnesium Chloride Struvite (Magnesium ammonium phosphate hexahydrate) Hydroxylapatite (Calcium hydroxyapatite) Potassium Chloride Ammonium Chloride Sodium Bicarbonate Citric Acid Nitric Acid Hydrochloric Acid

Ten substances that can potentially integrate the production of struvite were analysed and grouped in H3 criterion. In this case, minimisation of the use of these substances is required to support the development of a BBF formulation containing struvite compliant with the SSbD principles.

3.2.6. Humic and Fulvic Substances

Humic and fulvic substances are recognised as valuable bio-stimulants and fertiliser enhancers due to their ability to improve nutrient uptake, soil structure, and microbial activity (Lumactud et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2019). Recent advances have demonstrated their extraction from organic waste streams, such as sewage sludge, food waste, agro-industrial residues, and composted biomass, aligning with the principles of a circular and bio-based economy (Fernández-Delgado et al., 2023). The most common production methods include alkaline extraction, often using sodium or potassium hydroxide, sometimes combined with oxidative or enzymatic pre-treatments to enhance solubilisation. Several pilot and demonstration projects have shown promising results in producing humic and fulvic substances from digestates, compost, and vermicompost, with increased carbon recovery and nutrient content (Anielak et al., 2023). These recovered products are being assessed for their potential in soil amendment, crop stimulation, and nutrient chelation, contributing to more sustainable fertilisation strategies.

However, the production and agricultural application of humic and fulvic substances derived from waste streams must be guided by safety and risk assessments. Organic residues may contain contaminants such as heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants, antibiotic residues, or pathogenic

organisms. These can accumulate during the processing steps, potentially affecting soil quality, plant health, or food safety. Therefore, it is essential to ensure compliance with EU regulations (e.g., Fertilising Products Regulation (EU) 2019/1009) and to apply risk management frameworks, such as Safe-by-Design, to support safe innovation and market acceptance.

Several substances and materials were identified in the literature as relevant to produce humic and fulvic substances. These are listed in Table 3.22, along with their function and the process stage in which are typically applied.

Table 3.22 - List of relevant substances that may be used during the production of humic and fulvic substances.

Substance	Function	Stage
<i>Sodium hydroxide</i>	Strong base widely used in alkaline extraction processes to dissolve humic and fulvic fractions from dehydrated sludge, compost, or bio-waste.	Dehydrated Sludge Alkaline Treatment
<i>Sulphuric Acid</i>	Strong acid used to adjust pH post-alkaline extraction (typically to pH ~1–2), causing humic acids to precipitate while fulvic acids remain in solution.	Separation from Supernatant and Solid Fraction
<i>Citric Acid (alternative)</i>	Milder organic acid alternative for pH adjustment and precipitation. More environmentally friendly than mineral acids and sometimes preferred in eco-certified processes.	
<i>Humic and Fulvic acids</i>	End product	Solid fraction drying

The intrinsic hazard properties were identified, based on the information available in EU regulations, such as, REACH and CLP. In Table 3.23 the substances were grouped by the criteria established for the Step 1 of the SSbD framework.

Table 3.23 - List of assessed substances identified for the production of humic and fulvic substances, grouped by the corresponding SSbD criterion (H1, H2 and H3).

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H1	Sulphuric acid
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H2	_____

Group definition	Substances qualitatively assessed
Substances with hazard properties form Criterion H3	Citric Acid Sodium hydroxide Humic acids Fulvic acids

Figure 3.13 shows the hazard classification distribution of the 5 substances that can be involved in the production process of humic and fulvic substances, according to Step 1 of the SSbD framework.

Figure 3.13 - Hazard classification of the substances and materials typically used during the production of humic and fulvic substances

The qualitative assessment results reveal the following:

- 1 substance in group H1 (sulphuric acid) meaning it meets the criteria for Substances of Very High Concern (SVHCs) and requires priority for substitution under SSbD.
- 4 substances in group H3 amongst them are humic and fulvic substances. The other two are citric acid and sodium hydroxide, which if necessary to be used the quantities should be kept as minimum as possible, without compromising the functionality.

In line with SSbD principles, the use of citric acid presents an opportunity to reduce hazard classification while maintaining functionality. Depending on process efficiency and product quality requirements, citric acid may serve as a safer and more sustainable substitute for sulphuric acid in acidification and precipitation steps. Substituting H1 substances is a key objective of the SSbD framework to ensure that the entire production process, including intermediate reagents, complies with sustainability and safety goals.

4. Frameworks Used to Support BBFs Development

As aforementioned, the literature review of this task lays the foundation for the methodological framework in WP5: T5.2 to T5.5 aim to assess the sustainability of the production and use of the BBFs developed within the ReLEAF project. Thus, methodologies such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) will be performed. The referred methodologies will be briefly described in the next sub-sections.

4.1. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

The LCA methodology will be carried out within the scope of Task 5.3 and T5.5. This approach is regulated by the international standards ISO 14040:2006 (ISO, 2020a) and ISO 1044:2010 (ISO, 2020b). LCA is used to account for the potential environmental impact of a system (*e.g.*, products, processes or services) throughout its life cycle or part of it. Thus, this framework aims to identify the key environmental hotspots of a product system, inform stakeholders, and possibly support decisions towards the improvement of the overall environmental performance of the system. LCA can also be used to compare the environmental performance of alternative systems performing the same function, *e.g.*, compare a new system with a baseline system. Consequently, it allows to track the main environmental impact and benefits amongst alternatives and supports critical decisions, regarding general process improvement throughout a system's life cycle, *e.g.*, pollution prevention, and resource consumption reduction.

Following ISO standards, the LCA methodology Figure 4.1 has four interrelated steps, namely (1) Goal and scope definition; (2) Life cycle inventory analysis, (3) Life cycle impact assessment, and (4) Interpretation of results.

Figure 4.1 - Life cycle assessment (LCA) framework.

Overall, LCA may evaluate the environmental performance of a product system throughout its entire life cycle, from its cradle (usually with the extraction of raw materials and energy that is needed to produce the studied object) all the way to the grave, *i.e.*, waste management strategy applied to the object analysed. The assessment is accomplished by identifying quantitatively and qualitatively the

inputs (*e.g.*, energy and materials requirements) for each process included in the system under study, and the outputs, *e.g.*, emissions and waste materials released to the environment.

4.1.1. Comparative LCA of product use

For the comparative LCA of product use, the life cycle inventories of BBF production and agronomic data (nutrient content and yield data) are combined within the tool *FarmLCA* (de Baan et al., 2024) to assess selected environmental impacts (see Figure 4.2). The selection of the latter will be aligned with the LCA of production and will cover relevant impacts of fertiliser production and use such as eutrophication, climate warming, *etc.*

The *FarmLCA* tool combines standard life cycle inventory data for agronomic inputs and processes (*e.g.*, from Ecoinvent) with modelling of emissions to air, water and soil (*e.g.*, of nitrate, ammonia, methane or nitrous oxide) based on IPCC (2019) and EMEP/EEA Tier 1 and Tier 2 models (EMEP/EEA, 2019). Where applicable, the standard inventory data can be customised based on the field trial data from ReLEAF (*e.g.*, machinery use, pesticides applied, *etc.*).

The environmental impacts modelled with the *FarmLCA* tool are comparable based on a selected functional unit that relates to production (either per ha impact or kg of product produced). This allows to compare the BBF against conventional fertilisers. To promote a better understanding of uncertainties related to the comparison, the methodological framework also includes the parametrisation of key input parameters to conduct automatic sensitivity analyses.

Figure 4.2 - Comparative LCA of product use with the tool *farmLCA*.

4.2. Life Cycle Costing (LCC)

In order to determine whether there are economic advantages or disadvantages to the BBFs developed within the scope of ReLEAF project, the Life cycle costing (LCC) methodology will be performed jointly with the techno-economic assessment in T5.2. To do so, different approaches may be considered, namely the Process-based cost Model (PBCM) and Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA).

The PCBCM is an approach very useful to account for the main cost drivers, namely Material cost, Energy cost, Labour cost, and Equipment cost of a system. These costs may be further analysed considering the influence of the production volume, *i.e.*, they are divided into fixed and variable costs (Nadeau et al., 2010) (see Table 44.1).

Table 44.1 - Cost drivers and cost types of output by the PBCM.

Costs	Cost Driver	Cost type output
Material Cost	Consumables Cost	Variable Cost
	Solution Cost	Fixed Cost
Energy Cost	Energy Cost	Variable Cost
	Fixed Energy Cost	Fixed Cost
Labour Cost	Labour Cost	Variable Cost
Equipment Cost	Tank Cost	Fixed Cost
	Equipment Cost	Fixed Cost

The PBCM is divided into three sub-models, which are represented in Figure 4.3. The process model contains the general inputs of the process. It relates the product description (material, geometry, and size) and the process conditions required to produce it, such as part production cycle time.

Figure 4.3 - The PBCM structure.

The operation model contains the operating conditions of the process, which consider the number of shifts, working time, and production volume. This model calculates the necessary resources, namely equipment, labour, energy, among others, to produce the desired production volume, *i.e.*, the required inventory. Finally, the last sub-model is the financial model that contains the cost data

regarding the inputs used in the operations model, *e.g.*, cost per kg, cost per kWh. The model translates the inventory into fixed and variable costs (Nadeau et al., 2010).

On the other hand, the Material Flow Cost Accounting (MFCA) methodology (Figure 4.4) is defined by the international standard ISO 14051:2011 (ISO, 2011) and has as its main concept the mass flow balance that is based on the thermodynamic law: in any system, materials and energy could not be created or destroyed, just transformed. This method is characterized for being an accounting approach that is focused on the quantification of flows (materials and energy), in physic and monetary amounts. Furthermore, MFCA compares the costs that are associated with products and material losses (Sygulla et al., 2014). Thus, since it permits to identify the use of materials and resources (Bierer & Götze, 2012), clearly, it is an instrument effective to increase productivity, and, at the same time, reduces the costs and the environmental impacts of the production. MFCA analysis divides the process into quantity centres (QC) that could be parts of a process, where are quantified the inputs and outputs, firstly in physic amount and then, in monetary quantity. Both, material, and energy flows, must be described by a flow model in every QC. Figure 4.4 depicts an example of a flow model, considering just material movements (M. C. Rocha, 2006).

Figure 4.4 - Representation of the MFCA approach [Adapted from: A. Bierer et. Al, 2012].

The MFCA methodology considers a system of flows divided into: desired materials flow (products) and unwanted materials flow (wastes and losses). The latter could be, for example, material loss during the production and unsatisfactory products, materials that remain in the equipment after installation, auxiliary materials used like solvents and raw materials, work in progress and products in stock that are rejected because of several reasons, namely with damage.

The application of MFCA can be divided into four steps, according to the approach of the continuous improvement cycle: Plan-Do-Check-Act. Firstly, in the plan phase, it must be understood the practicability, the advantages, and the value of MFCA. Then, in the do stage, it is identified the inputs (*e.g.*, materials and energy) and outputs (*e.g.*, mass and energy losses) for each QC that should be quantified in physic units. To calculate the material flows, all of the physic units have to be in a single and standard unit. After gathering and validating the data, the material flows are converted into monetary units to support decision-making. Since each process needs an entry of labour, depreciation, energy, transport, among other costs, the MFCA adds all of the cost information to the quantity data.

Thus, the economic loss can be analysed, not only concerning materials, but also including all of the manufacturing costs. Regarding the last stage, the interpretation of the results obtained after the MFCA analysis will allow the identification of the most relevant QC in terms of material losses. Also, they can be analysed with more detail to identify the causes of inefficiencies and the reasons that are causing costs. The general information can support a wide range of decisions to improve both, the environmental and economic performance.

4.3. Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA)

Aiming to assess the social impacts of the innovative BBFs developed under the scope of the ReLEAF project, the Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA) methodology will be applied. This approach will follow the ISO standard ISO 14075, and also ISO 14040 and ISO 14044. Moreover, to develop the life cycle inventory, the UNEP Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products approach will be also considered. The impact categories will be chosen according to the UNEP-SETAC Social LCA and ISO 14075 guidelines and the most potential indicators for workers, local community, and society will be studied, *e.g.*, Fair Wage, Working Time, Public Living Condition, Technology Development, and Contribution to the Economy.

The s-LCA is a methodology used to evaluate the social and socioeconomic impacts of products throughout their entire life cycle. Similarly to the environmental assessment, S-LCA comprises four main stages Figure 4.5, namely (1) Definition of Goal and Scope, (2) Inventory Analysis, (3) Impact Assessment, and (4) Interpretation of Results (UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative, 2009).

Figure 4.5 - Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) framework.

Overall, the S-LCA framework aims to evaluate the social and socioeconomic impacts of products throughout their entire life cycle, as well as identify and analyse the critical social hotspots of the product's life cycle. Additionally, this approach may provide useful information during the decision-making process to different stakeholders (*e.g.*, consumers and workers), companies, and governments. Finally, this is a key methodology to promote transparency and social accountability along a product's value chain. In other words, the S-LCA is a valuable tool for assessing and improving the social performance of products, contributing to the promotion of sustainable development.

5. Conclusions and Further Work

The present deliverable aimed to (1) highlight the main environmental concerns associated with bio-based fertilisers through a literature review, (2) carry out a qualitative assessment of the safety of chemicals and materials consumed during the BBFs' formulations, and (3) describe the methodologies used to perform the sustainability assessment that will be considered along the project, *i.e.*, LCA, LCC, and S-LCA.

After performing the literature review about the sustainability of BBFs, some conclusions may be highlighted. System design and integration are crucial when assessing the environmental performance of different systems. Studies suggest that decentralised and integrated systems (like HRAP and nutrient recovery) perform better environmentally than centralised methods. This supports the use of locally produced bio-based fertilisers for nutrient recycling, resource conservation, and circular economy goals. However, recovery efficiency and bioavailability vary among BBF types, affecting their performance. Other studies indicate that BBFs maintain agronomic effectiveness and may even improve soil quality and reduce nitrogen losses, generally not compromising crop yields or quality.

From the environmental point of view, hotspots identified for the BBFs' production include electricity consumption, especially from non-renewable sources, and the use of some consumables during nutrient recovery, *e.g.*, sodium hydroxide and magnesium oxide. When considered, emissions (CO₂, NH₃, N₂O, and NO_x) may also be a great contributor to environmental burdens. Economically, BBF production can lower costs compared to synthetic fertilisers, but high initial investments and chemical inputs can be a barrier. From a socioeconomic perspective, public perception, regulation, and market development are essential for a wider adoption, despite concerns about health and safety.

The limitations found in the literature include the existence of studies that often rely on small-scale lab data or models that do not reflect industrial production, leading to scalability issues and a lack of validation with real-world data. Also, life-cycle emissions, such as CO₂, NH₃, and N₂O, are frequently neglected or modelled (using theoretical models), which underestimates environmental impacts. Additionally, sustainability assessments may neglect transport, long-term soil effects, and the entire life cycle of BBFs. Finally, there is also a need to integrate LCA with economic and social evaluations to have a broader and more comprehensive overview of the sustainability of the production and application of bio-based fertilisers.

The described LCA, LCC, and s-LCA methodologies will be performed in the next years according to the development from T5.2 to T5.5.

A qualitative hazard assessment was conducted for substances identified as potentially suitable for integration into the production processes of the ReLEAF project's bio-based fertiliser ingredients. This assessment focused on intrinsic hazard properties as defined in European regulatory sources, including the CLP Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 and the REACH database managed by ECHA. Substances were screened in accordance with Step 1 of the SSbD framework, which includes classification under hazard groups H1 to H3 and applies a cut-off criterion for Substances of Very High Concern (SVHCs).

The results indicate that most assessed substances fall within Group H3, reflecting low intrinsic hazard based on current data. However, several substances were classified under Group H1 due to their recognised harmful properties and relevance as an SVHC, underscoring the need for prioritising substitution or reformulation in line with the SSbD principle of hazard minimisation at the design stage. Substances such as citric acid for instance, while not hazard-free (group H3), may represent viable lower-hazard alternatives, subject to performance and process compatibility.

The results of the qualitative hazard assessment will be integrated into Deliverable 6.12 – SSbD Recommendations, which will support the identification of safer process chemicals, prioritisation of redesign options, and informed decision-making to promote compliance, hazard reduction, and sustainability across the ReLEAF value chain.

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Annex

The list of substances identified as potentially suitable for integration into the production processes of ReLEAF's ingredients for bio-based fertiliser formulations (BFFs), along with their classification based on intrinsic hazard properties from EU regulatory databases (e.g. ECHA, CLP), is provided in the accompanying Excel annex titled *D5.1 Annex Section – List of Substances – Qualitative Hazard Assessment* that can be found in Zenodo repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15557771>